

Skills 4 eosc

Deliverable D4.2: Learning paths for data professionals

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Deliverable Abstract

This final deliverable for Skills4EOSC Work Package 4 (WP4) "Curricula and Learning Paths for Open Science-Ready Institutions" presents the outcomes of Task 4.2 on Learning Paths for Data Professionals. It offers an executive overview and synthesis of detailed reports that document the design, implementation, evaluation, and refinement of three distinct learning paths focused on open licensing, reproducible research, and ethical-legal-social issues (ELSI). These learning paths were co-created by a distributed team and piloted with learners across Europe. The report captures instructional strategies, content reuse practices, quality assurance processes, and alignment with Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) profiles. It also discusses key challenges such as platform usability, time constraints, and the learning curve for new

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tools like GitHub. The deliverable contributes actionable insights for developing FAIR-by-Design (FbD) learning content and offers recommendations for broader institutional adoption.

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Executive summary

This deliverable compiles and analyses the results of Task 4.2 within the Skills4EOSC project, which developed and piloted three targeted learning paths for data professionals:

1. Open Licenses for Data, Software, and Code
2. Technical Skills for Reproducible Research
3. Train-the-Trainer Asynchronous Workshop for Ethical and Legal Professionals (ELSI)

Each learning path is grounded in the FAIR-by-Design (FbD) methodology and aligns with evolving MVS (Minimum Viable Skillset) profiles for data stewards and legal experts. The report includes rich documentation of the instructional design process, feedback from participants, quality assurance reviews, and strategies for content reuse and dissemination via platforms like GitHub¹ and Zenodo².

Key insights include:

- The FbD methodology promoted collaborative and modular content development but introduced challenges due to varying digital skills and limited time.
- GitHub served as an effective dissemination tool, although its use required significant upskilling.
- The Skills4EOSC learning platform³'s interface complexity hindered some teaching and learning experiences.
- The quality assurance process enhanced the pedagogical and technical rigor of the materials, with emphasis on accessibility, structure, and clarity.
- Participant feedback confirmed increased knowledge and high satisfaction but highlighted the need for more time, clearer examples, and glossary support.

¹ <https://fair-by-design-methodology.github.io/microlearning/latest/>

² <https://zenodo.org/records/11548062>

³ <https://learning.skills4eosc.eu/>

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Overall, the deliverable not only provides reusable learning resources but also offers a tested framework for collaborative and high-quality Open Science training, adaptable across institutions and professional roles.

Introduction

1.1 Designing the learning paths

The learning paths followed the FAIR-by-Design (FbD) methodology developed in WP2, T2.3.

We started to design the first learning path before the FbD microlearning site was produced, so we made a huge excel sheet depicting the stages of the FbD method with a timeline of implementation of each stage in the creation of the learning content. This approach really helped us break the Fair-by-Design methodology into actions that we used to steer meetings, produce a Gantt-like chart timeline for development and really dive into the FbD methodology and master it as a workflow in the development of the learning paths that followed.

We searched for reusable content and kept a record of these searches in Excel, where we also commented on the pros and cons of using the materials and investigated potentials for reuse (licences). Consequently, as a development team we improved our knowledge of licensing in the context of open educational resources.

We used GitHub to make a downloadable and editable repository of the training materials. Where more than one training was held for a learning path, both trainings are collected in the one repository. Github was a new tool for many of the content developers, which added an extra layer of complexity to the FbD method. Therefore, we used known tools such as slides and shared documents to brainstorm and visualise the learning content before moving over to Github which was used primarily as a tool to publish the final content in a reusable and editable format.

1.2 Challenges and lessons learned

1.2.1 Learning Path design

Tools Used

The project relied heavily on the FAIRbyDesign materials developed by WP2, T2.3. Initially, we designed the learning path before the FbD microlearning site and workshop was produced and held, which led us to create a comprehensive Excel sheet (Figure 1) depicting the stages of the FbD method with a timeline for implementation. The complete excel sheet is available on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15573726>

Figure 1: Section of preliminary approach to FbD

GitHub was utilized to make downloadable and editable repositories of the training materials, consolidating both trainings into one repository. We searched for reusable content and maintained a record of these searches in Excel, commenting on the pros and cons of using the materials and investigating potentials for reuse, including licensing considerations. PowerPoint was employed for brainstorming and structuring content, while Google Docs was chosen for creating collaborative writing documents. Polls and other interactive activities on the Skills4EOOSC learning platform were explored to engage learners. We decided across all online training

developed by the task to turn off the slides during teaching to engage in face-to-face discussions with the learners.

What Went Well

The FAIR by Design (FbD) method proved to be a great didactic and collaborative approach to design of learning content. Collaborative slide development was effective, and the instructional design process encouraged us to consider deeper learning outcomes. Our confidence with the FAIR by Design method increased throughout the development of the learning paths. Consequently, as a task-group, our own competences have improved as well as the competencies of our learners. We made mistakes, but look forward to applying it to other types of learning objects and training materials in our local contexts. Everyone who was part of developing the learning content could find a workflow within the FbD process that they could apply straight away as well as areas that required up-skilling before application. In our task group for example, some of us used GitHub for the first time and will continue to use it in the design and publishing of learning content after the Skills4EOSC project is closed. Others enjoyed working with the quality assurance processes and took the role upon themselves to be the in-group “expert” and lead the evaluation the accessibility of all the learning materials produced by the task. Accessibility in the teaching pedagogy context was explored as the technical accessibility and also learner accessibility, including readability. The quality assurance process forced us to prioritize content, which improved the delivery and the reception of the content.

Challenges

The main challenge in the task and amongst the learners was the lack of knowledge in how to use the Skills4EOSC learning platform, including how activities designed using the platform work in practice and how different the functionalities of the online teaching room were compared to other systems the instructors and learners know well, e.g. compared to Zoom or Teams. In the feedback from the learners and instructors it was very clear that the

Skills4EOSC online teaching room added a layer of complexity to already complex subjects taught on the learning paths.

Keeping the learning paths to two hours was also challenging. The FAIR by Design methodology forced us to take a modular approach to the design of the learning content and ensured alignment with the learning objective. The QA considerations ensured the teaching materials, were readable, easy to follow and accessible. Yet still, we were too ambitious with the amount of material we attempted to cover in the two hours. Ultimately, we elected to share the cut material while tailoring what we kept to concise learning objectives. Further, the milestone in February for completion of the first pilot was too optimistic as it was November before the task group had been trained in the FbD method.

The FAIR by Design method involved a lot of work with a steep learning curve, due to varying levels of understanding of the methods and levels of expertise in the tools, exacerbated by time pressure from everyday work assignments not related to the project. Consequently, task members had little time to dedicate to learning and implementing new skills such as co-creating content in Github. To work efficiently the task group divided into three sub-groups: 1) instructors and developers of learning content, 2) persons dedicated to learning and undertaking the quality assurance, and 3) “administrators” who facilitated the FbD workflow including publishing the learning paths in Github, Zenodo and on the Learning Platform. This division of labour resulted in double efforts in creating slides in the workplace, making a GitHub repository, and transferring information to the repository, and then creating a post in Zenodo but at the same time enabled peer learning within the task group. Consequently, as a task group we have all increased our knowledge of the topics taught in the learning paths AND understood the requirements to the FbD process and the skills needed to produce FbD content.

Lessons Learned

The FbD method is a good approach that we would like to implement locally, but it should be approached pragmatically. Rather than broad and full implementation, FbD could be adopted in stages, with institutions,

organisations and workers proceeding when they are comfortable. The Skills4EOSC Workspace was fine for collaboration but the platform has limitations for example in rights to delete and move slides produced by others in the working group, resulting in a folder and file structure containing duplicates and unfinished files that could not be deleted.

GitHub was useful for developing learning content and instructor notes, allowing reuse and repurposing. In our task we approached GitHub as a platform for disseminating content and providing an editable format of the learning materials. Consequently, we circumnavigated the need to work directly in Github in content development as skills in Github were limited in our task group.

Developing the FbD learning paths was a huge learning experience that is continuing to impact how we develop learning content now the project is finished. Through practice, we understood what FbD entails, made mistakes, and are looking forward to applying the methods to other types of learning objects and implementing FbD at our own organisations. Examples of which are the development of workshops in FbD at the Royal Library, Denmark⁴ and adaption of learning paths by CSC Finland⁵

1.2.2 Quality assurance process

Accessible resources help instructors connect with and involve individuals of diverse abilities and situations, fostering a flexible and learner-centered environment. In the context of Skills4EOSC the quality assessment⁶ is structured around four sub-frameworks—Generic (G-SF), Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS-SF), FAIR-by-design (FAIR-SF), and Ethical, Legal, and Social Issues (ELSI-SF). Each sub-framework introduces essential and non-essential indicators, checklist-based evaluations, and best practices to guide the

⁴Presentation INCONECSS, May 2025:

<https://www.inconecss.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/inconecss-2025-slides-engelsmann-wildgaard.pdf>

⁵ Licensing data and code – Key steps towards reusability workshop: <https://csc.fi/en/training-calendar/licensing-data-and-code-key-steps-towards-reusability/>

⁶ <https://www.skills4eosc.eu/resources/quality-assurance-certification-framework>

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development, assessment, and potential certification of Open Science training materials. The accessibility component emphasizes the functionality of teaching materials, ensuring they are easily usable by as many people and technologies as possible.

Being aware that the learning path would undergo an external assessment of its visual, didactic, and accessibility qualities compelled us to critically reflect on our ambitions. From the outset of developing the learning path, we aimed to deliver content that is both technically proficient and of high quality which ultimately helped with the overall delivery of the material in a pedagogical frame. As a task group, we did not experience awareness of the quality assurance criteria a hindrance to creativity in the development stage.

One team member was responsible for the QA process. We found this to be beneficial, as the process required a close attention to detail and impartiality in assessing the content. This team member became the go-to expert in the QA process for the task group, and provided written reports and face-to-face feedback which in turn up-skilled the task group in how to understand and apply the detailed and comprehensive QA criteria developed by T2.4.

Table 1 – Overview of main areas for improvement identified during the QA process

QA theme	Description
Terminology and Structure	Use consistent terminology as defined in FbD for different parts of the learning path. Divide the slide deck into separate parts for each unit to facilitate easier navigation and better organization on the learning platform.
Slide Deck Organization	Each unit should have a separate learning unit plan, learning objectives, learners' notebook, facilitation guide, activities, and slide deck. Ensure that each unit includes an introduction to the trainers and trainees, housekeeping information, and learning objectives.
Accessibility	Ensure all slides have unique titles for screen reader

	navigation. Provide alternative text for all images. Check the reading order of slide content for screen readers. Ensure sufficient contrast for readability. Export slides to an accessible format (e.g., PDF) and perform another round of accessibility checks.
Slide Design Consistency	Use consistent font sizes and types throughout the slide decks. Maintain a uniform color scheme and ensure titles and main text use the same font and size across all slides.
Attributions	Follow the TASL model (Title, Author, Source, License) for all attributions. Ensure all images and resources are properly cited with complete information.
Hyperlinks	Use descriptive text for hyperlinks instead of displaying URLs. Ensure all links are properly formatted and accessible.
Content Clarity and Readability	Ensure text on slides is readable with a minimum font size of 18. Avoid using too many different font sizes and styles. Check the resolution of images to ensure text within images is legible.
Unit specific improvements	Each unit should have a clear title and introduction. Include Q&A, assessment information, and feedback gathering in the wrap-up section. Ensure that all slides are properly titled and that the content is logically organized.

1.2.3 Co-creation

An invitation to review the subject matter of each learning path was sent out across the Skills4EOSC workpackages, likewise WP4 members were invited to review the individual reports of each set of learning paths before publication in Zenodo. Further the learning paths contributed to the development of content and themes in the T4.1 Data Steward Curriculum, the T2.1 MVS profiles, particularly MVS Data Steward and MVS Legal Expert, and T2.3 FAIR-by-Design Methodology.

2 Overview of Learning Paths and key observations

Three distinct Learning Paths were created by T4.2 and held as multiple workshops. The mission to enhance the skills and knowledge of professionals in various domains related to research data management, the legal aspects, and technical skills for reproducible research. The workshops were held at different times, locations and in different formats with the aim to target specific groups of professionals. Below is a brief overview of each learning path and key observations. A detailed report for each learning path is found in the appendices of this report.

2.1 Learning Path : Open Licenses for Data, Software, and Code

Table 2 – Overview of learning path: Open Licenses for Data, Software and Code

Date of training	June 3rd and 22nd October 2024.
Instructors	Agnes Jasinska (DCC)
Facilitators	Lorna Wildgaard (DKB), Benjamin Derksen (DKB)
Content description	Importance of licensing research outputs, considerations before applying licenses, and the application process of licenses.

Training materials and evaluative report:

- Included as Appendix A in this report
- Milestone: Pilot learning path for Data Stewards:
<https://zenodo.org/records/13309349>
- Open Licenses for Data (Training materials):
<https://zenodo.org/records/14921877>
- Open Licenses for Data, Software and Code (Github integration):
<https://zenodo.org/records/12703494>

Summary:

Learners were satisfied or very satisfied with the training. The majority would recommend the learning path to colleagues. Post-training evaluations indicated an improvement in knowledge about research software, copyright, and licensing. The learners recommended increasing the duration of the training to allow more time for discussions and exercises or reduce content to fit the allocated time and increase focus on discussions.

The instructor and learning path developers identified the need to develop additional training materials to address software and code licensing in more depth.

Alignment with MVS Data Steward

Covers essential skills and competencies for Data Stewards, particularly in open licensing for research data, software, and code. Highlights the need for including more detailed knowledge of copyright and licensing in the MVS for Data Stewards.

Recommends including a section dedicated to legal aspects of RDM, especially regarding FAIR data dissemination and sharing in compliance with legal recommendations.

2.2 Learning Path: Technical Skills for Reproducible Research

Table 3 – Overview of learning path: technical skills for Reproducible Research

Date of training	January 17th and January 31st 2025
Instructors	Agnes Jasinska (DCC), Tuulikki Alamettåå (TUNI), Vojdan Kjorveziroski (UKIM), and Mareike Buss (CBS).
Facilitators	Lorna Wildgaard (DKB), Benjamin Derksen (DKB)
Content description	Theoretical and practical aspects of supporting reproducibility in data management workflows, including hands-on instruction in data hygiene and file versioning.

Training materials and evaluative report:

- Included as Appendix B in this report
- Technical Skills are the Bridge to Reproducible Research: An introduction for Data Librarians (Report): <https://zenodo.org/records/14936648>
- Technical Skills are the Bridge to Reproducible Research: An introduction for Data Librarians (Training materials): <https://zenodo.org/records/14893262>
- Technical Skills are the Bridge to Reproducible Research: <https://zenodo.org/uploads/15025016>

Summary

Participants appreciated the comprehensive overview of the reproducibility crisis that created a foundation and context for the practical introduction to technical skills required to mitigate them. The participants used a common case and tools (GitHub, Jupyter Notebook, materials on the Learning Platform)

to delve deeper into the topics discussed and try after the workshop to apply their new technical skills. This possibility to try technical solutions with the opportunity to discuss with fellow participants from various scientific disciplines was highly valued.

Future improvements point to providing real-life examples, especially for complex topics such as Fabrication, Falsification, Plagiarism, and the workflow in GitHub. It was suggested to integrate the principles and practices of Open Science throughout the discussions and include more detailed discussions and examples related to the challenges of reproducing qualitative research.

Alignment with MVS Data Steward

The skills and competences were aligned with the MVS for Data Stewards. The MVS describes the Data Librarian as an associated function title under the major category of Coordinator Data Steward. Recommended additions to the MVS are:

- The addition of a basic knowledge of “closed” science research practices such that the data librarian/coordinator data steward will be able to successfully navigate and mediate the arguments of researchers, who act according to a variety of incentives. These incentives are not always aligned with Open Science, and the data librarian/coordinator data steward will have to be able to offer rhetorical rebuttals in training situations.
- Addition of the crucial skill was that someone in this role be an “Open Science warrior.” While this may not be a common element to every data steward, we recommend it be included for those data stewards working specifically with research data.

2.3 Train the Trainer Asynchronous Workshop for Ethical and Legal Professionals (ELSI):

Table 4 – Overview of learning path: an asynchronous workshop for ELSI

Date of training	February 3rd and March 7th 2025
Instructors	Mareike Buss (CBS).
Facilitators	Lorna Wildgaard (DKB), Benjamin Derksen (DKB)
Content description	Asynchronous workshop following the "off the wall" design principle, with no instructor but a host facilitating discussions. The asynchronous workshop its self consists of 10 modules. The aim of the modules is to provide the information on why ELSI is important in Open Science and how ELSI professionals can help support researchers work openly as possible. The modules are a mix of theoretical information and practical activities focusing on analysis of common ELSI related use cases and scenarios that OS researchers face in their everyday practice.

Training materials and evaluative report:

- Included as Appendix C in this report
- ELSI perspectives in Open Science: An asynchronous workshop - A report of the Train the Trainers at Copenhagen University Library and Copenhagen Business School : <https://zenodo.org/records/14982498>
- ELSI perspectives in Open Science: An asynchronous workshop (training materials): <https://zenodo.org/records/12703279>

Summary

The workshop can be opened up to a broader audience, including PIs, decision-makers, and legal experts, as advised in the alignment of the MVS, below. The main learning outcome experienced by the participants was their

Improved awareness about different understandings and applications of legal terminology. This was a big Aha! moment.

The intention of the asynchronous approach was to create a “plug and play” workshop that did not require an instructor. However, a facilitator proved to be essential to guide the participants through the materials and act as a content “curator” to tailor discussions to fit the backgrounds of the participants. The curator is recommended to take “a pick-and-mix” approach to the materials, thus creating a more flexible, audience-specific workshop content and considered delivery. This way the materials can be adapted to different curators, who may have a stronger or weaker relationship with the materials, and thus may be more or less comfortable assuming a more traditional teaching role.

Importantly, the materials require better pacing, improved AI narration, and more inclusive coverage of qualitative research. Time spent on video “lectures” could be reduced in favor of case-based learning and activities which is where we experienced deeper learning and reflection happened.

Participants in both workshops underlined the usefulness of potentially sharing the workshop with researchers as well as other stakeholders to help further understand the reception and understanding of ELSI aspects in Open Science. Finally, they drew attention to the amount of new concepts introduced during the workshop and accordingly the need for a glossary of terms. The glossary was quickly added to the learning materials by the creators of the Learning Path.

Alignment with MVS Legal Expert

The workshop strengthens in particular, the ELSI professionals’ empathy and understanding of the challenges researchers face in working openly. During the workshops the participants awareness about the different understandings and application of legal terminology across the organisation, research projects, disciplinary perspectives was improved. The suggested MVS revisions include:

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- clarifying the distinction between skills and competences in GDPR and IPR,
- emphasizing their practical application for PIs. The term “empathy” should
- be added as a soft skill, as it enhances inclusive policies and researcher
- support.

The workshop’s relevance extends beyond Legal Experts to MVS RI professionals and MVS Policy Makers, highlighting the extensive legal knowledge required for advising on (open) research regulations.

Appendixes

The following appendixes provide detailed documentation and supporting materials for the three learning paths developed and piloted in Task 4.2. Each appendix includes the training content, evaluation findings, and key observations related to a specific learning path. These materials demonstrate the application of the FAIR-by-Design methodology and are intended to support reuse and adaptation by other institutions and training providers. All materials are openly available through Zenodo for continued dissemination and collaborative development.

- Appendix A: Pilot Learning Path for Data Stewards – Open Licenses for Data, Software, and Code
- Appendix B: Technical Skills Are the Bridge to Reproducible Research – An Introduction for Data Librarians
- Appendix C: ELSI Perspectives in Open Science – An Asynchronous Train-the-Trainer Workshop

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Milestone: Pilot learning path for Data Stewards

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Deliverable Abstract

This is a short report on the pilot ToT Learning Path for Data Stewards designed by the Skills4EOSC project, WP4, T4.2. the EOSC. The report summarises the training and points to areas for improvement regarding the content and delivery of the training and further, alignment with the MVS Data Steward which is a competency profile also developed within Skills4EOSC.

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Milestone: Pilot learning path for Data Stewards

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<i>v.n</i>			

TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

<i>Terminology/Acronym</i>	<i>Definition</i>

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1 Executive summary

Overview of the Learning Path Pilot

On the 3rd of June, an online pilot for the learning path “Open Licenses for Data, Software, and Code” was conducted using Big Blue Button as the meeting platform. Participants accessed materials published on the Skills4EOSC learning platform. The training was facilitated by Agnes Jasinska (DCC) and Lorna Wildgaard (DKB), with technical support from Andrea Corleto and Gabriella Paolini (GARR). The content was divided into three units covering the importance of licensing research outputs, considerations before applying licenses, and the application process of licenses. Post-training, learners completed a homework assignment advising a fictive project PI on licensing their research outputs, fostering a collaborative learning environment.

Participant Evaluation Results

Thirty-three learners participated, with eighteen completing the evaluation survey (54% response rate). Seventeen respondents were satisfied or very satisfied with the pilot, and one was neutral. Sixteen respondents would recommend the learning path to colleagues. Most participants had intermediate to expert knowledge of Open Science principles, FAIR principles, and research data, but were novices to intermediates in research software, copyright, and licensing. Post-training evaluations indicated an improvement in knowledge about research software, copyright, and particularly licensing, which was the core focus of the training.

Positive Aspects and Areas for Improvement of the ToT

Participants praised the professional knowledge and communication skills of the instructor, the clarity and conciseness of the content, and the useful discussions that enhanced learning. Highlights included a congenial atmosphere, practical tools, and effective group activities. However, the two-hour duration was deemed too short, and more time was suggested for discussions and exercises. To optimise future training, it is recommended to reduce content to fit the allocated time and increase focus on discussions.

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Additional training materials should be developed to address software and code licensing in more depth.

Technical Platform Evaluation

Technical difficulties with Big Blue Button significantly impacted the learning experience, necessitating better training and practice with the platform. The Big Blue Button platform added complexity to the training, with issues like slide upload problems, formatting changes, and navigation challenges between break-out rooms and the main room. Recommendations include sufficient training and practice with both Big Blue Button and the Learning Platform to avoid disruptions in future sessions.

Alignment with MVS for Data Stewards

The training covered essential skills and competencies for Data Stewards, particularly in open licensing for research data, software, and code. The pilot highlighted the need for including more detailed knowledge of copyright and licensing in the MVS for Data Stewards.

The MVS Data Steward should include a section dedicated to legal aspects of RDM, especially regarding FAIR data dissemination and sharing in compliance with legal recommendations. The pilot demonstrated the need for comprehensive knowledge for each concept listed in the MVS and the importance of operational training materials that go beyond the MVS, relevant also for legal experts and ELSI professionals.

Sources for Learning Path Development

The learning path was hosted on the [Skills4EOSC Learning Platform](#) and was adapted from content available in an [editable library of training materials on Github](#) developed by Task 4.2. Together, these sources provide a foundation for creating a comprehensive and effective learning path on open licenses for data, software, and code in local contexts.

2 A brief description of the pilot training (ToT) and descriptive feedback from the evaluation

2.1 Brief description of Learning Path pilot

On the 3rd of June, the pilot for the learning path “Open Licenses for Data, Software and Code was held”. The pilot was held online using the the Big Blue Button as the online meeting room and participants were asked to access materials published on the Skills4EOSC learning platform during the pilot. The pilot was facilitated learning, with the content divided into three units each containing discussions and learning activities. :

1. Why you should license your research output and how to overcome resistance (slides 7 - 22)
2. What to consider before applying licenses to research outputs (slides 23-73)
3. How to apply licenses to research output (slides 75 - 105)

The slides used in the pilot can be found on the Skills4EOSC learning platform and are published in the Skills4EOSC Zenodo library, please refer to Section 5 of this report for more information. After the training, the learners were invited to complete a homework assignment. The assignment was to use knowledge learned during the pilot to advise a fictive project PI on how to license their research output. The learners were requested to post their advice on the Learning Platform, thus creating a forum where others can read and learn from the responses.

Materials used in the pilot were adapted from the WP4, T4.2 milestone which contains a library of slides for the trainer to choose from dependent on the focus of the training event, instructor notes, glossary, activities, suggestions for evaluation questions and competency badge (Section 5).

Agnes Jasinska (DCC) was the instructor and designed the materials used in the pilot. Lorna Wildgaard (DKB) was the facilitator and Agnes' sparring

partner in the lead-up to the pilot. Andrea Corleto (GARR) and Gabriella Paolini (GARR) provided technical support prior and during the pilot.

2.2 Results of the participants evaluation of the pilot

Thirty-three learners participated in the pilot of the learning path. Eighteen learners completed the evaluation, giving a response rate of 54%. Seventeen of the respondents to the evaluation survey were either satisfied or very satisfied and 1 participant expressed neutrality. The professional profiles of the learners is presented in Table 1, the “other” category was indicated by a data steward:

Table 1: Professional profiles of the 18 learners who responded to the evaluation survey

Response	Average	Total
Researcher	17%	3
Research support staff	44%	8
Research infrastructure professional	11%	2
Trainer (on data related topics)	17%	3
Service provider	6%	1
Other	6%	1
Total responses to question		18/18

Sixteen of the respondents would recommend the learning path to a colleague. The majority of the learners described themselves as having intermediate to expert knowledge in Open Science principles, FAIR principles

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and research data, and novice to intermediate knowledge of research software, copyright and licensing (Table 2).

Table 2: Participants knowledge of each area prior to participating in learning path

Responses	Novice	Intermediate	Expert	Total
Open Science principles	1 (6%)	5 (29%)	11 (65%)	17
FAIR principles	1 (6%)	3 (18%)	13 (76%)	17
Research data	1 (6%)	9 (53%)	7 (41%)	17
Research software	7 (41%)	9 (53%)	1 (6%)	17
Copyright	6 (35%)	10 (59%)	1 (6%)	17
Licensing	4 (24%)	11 (65%)	2 (12%)	17

After the training, the participants rated if their knowledge of the above topics had improved (Table 3, next page). Unsurprisingly, no vast improvement in their knowledge about Open Science principles, FAIR principles or Research data was acknowledged as the majority of learners were confident in these topics prior to training. The learners confirmed a somewhat increase in knowledge about research software and copyright and a considerable increase in their knowledge about licensing which was the core learning objectives of the training.

Table 3: Participants knowledge of each area after participating in learning path

Responses	Not really	Somewhat	Considerably	Total
Open Science principles	9 (53%)	8 (47%)	0	17
FAIR principles	10 (59%)	6 (35%)	1 (6%)	17
Research data	9 (53%)	7 (41%)	1 (6%)	17
Research software	6 (35%)	10 (59%)	1 (6%)	17
Copyright	1 (6%)	12 (71%)	4 (24%)	17
Licensing	0	8 (47%)	9 (53%)	17

The instructor was complimented for her professional knowledge and skills as a communicator of the complex topic of Open Licenses. The content was presented in a simple, clear and concise manner with useful discussions between participants that framed the flow of the materials and enhanced deeper learning. Even participants with existing knowledge of the subject came away from the training with new insights. All respondents to the evaluation scored the content as highly relevant, present clearly, good pace, useful activities, an effective instructor who created a good learning environment.

We asked the pilot participants in the evaluations: Were there any related topics not covered that you think should be added? In their responses, rather than proposing other, related topics, our participants mostly expressed a desire to examine the topic of licensing in more depth (and to have more time to do so). They asked for more examples of different projects and licenses; to learn more about software licenses in particular; to better understand the role and support of repositories in shaping the choice of the license; and to discuss dual licensing. The question of the impact of open licensing on a researcher’s career also came up, evoking the broader discussion about academic research culture and the still often insufficient

incentives and rewards for researchers who openly share their research outputs and engage in Open Science.

Below, is a summary of what the respondents considered went well and where there is room for improvement.

What went well and useful content

- The congenial atmosphere
- Mitigation strategies
- Arguments to convince researchers to licence their work and dispelling misconceptions
- Exchanges in break-out rooms
- The richness of the content that can be adapted locally
- Links to and advice on practical tools
- The examples and cases used throughout the training
- Highlighting learning objectives at the start of the training/unit and wrapping up each unit with key take-aways and activities

Room for improvement

- The two hour learning path is too short for such a big topic. Reduce the content to avoid superficially addressing some content
- More time on group discussions. Some groups worked really well as a small group, others didn't interact as well. More time would allow the instructor to visit the groups and ensure the members have understood the assignment and perhaps kick-start the conversation
- More time dedicated to licensing software and code
- More exercises
- More time on activities – activity 2 could be placed after the unit about different licensing options. This could result in deeper and less abstract discussions
- Using multiple platforms was not a success, the shift from the learning platform, break out groups and main group on the Big Blue Button was not easy.

The major criticism from all participants were technical difficulties using the Big Blue Button which disrupted the teaching, causing delays and confusion. These are addressed in the next section.

2.3 Evaluation of the Big Blue Button and the Skills4EOSC Learning Platform

The Big Blue Button (BBB) is the online meeting room recommended in the Skills4EOSC project. However, in this pilot we experienced the BBB as adding an extra layer of complexity to conducting the training and many participants commented negatively impacted their experience. Prior to the training we coordinated with GARR on how to use the BBB. However, even with this preparation and technical support during the ToT, the training suffered technical difficulties. Thankfully the Tech support team were present during the pilot and saved the workshop.

If the training is to happen on the BBB and Learning Platform, then everyone in Skills4EOSC needs:

- sufficient training on the BBB
- sufficient practice on the BBB - for example: the WP meetings could be on the BBB, to let all of us get familiar with it and practice using the various features
- Sufficient practice using the Learning Platform
- Awareness that creating learning activities and adding content to the Learning Platform takes time that needs to be allocated in the development of the learning path

Difficulties experienced during the pilot are listed below and can be used to inform training in the BBB:

- Not being able to upload slides to the BBB
- Changes to slide content during import, formatting issues on the uploaded slides, missing animations and missing text,

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- Not being able to to set up polls or break-out groups prior to the ToT
- Not being able to reuse break-out rooms
- Navigation for learners between break-out rooms and the main room (Note: this is an experience issue as most people are used to Teams or Zoom. On the BBB the break-out room opens in a new tab, so learners switch between the break-out room and the main room by clicking on the tab
- Sound issues when returning to the main group. We found out that reloading the page solved this issue
- Break out groups, with a timer on, end abruptly. No message that the rooms are closing is transmitted. There is a timer at the top of each break-out room – draw attention to it!
- If no timer is set on a break-out room, the break-out rooms have to be closed manually – the instructor/facilitator must broadcast to each group, one at a time, that it is time to return to the main room
- The learners in the break out rooms can click on the message “leave meeting” to return to the main room. This caused confusion, as it was interpreted as “leave the entire meeting”

2.4 Participants evaluation and alignment with the MVS for data stewards

In terms of the skills and competencies covered in the pilot, as the title suggests, the main focus was on open licenses for research data, software, and code. Four learning objectives were shared with the students:

- Explain the different types of licenses that can be applied to FAIR research outputs in accordance with regulations, policies and other requirements.
- Apply an appropriate license to a research output.
- Argue for the choice of appropriate licenses to research output and for the importance of creating machine-readable licenses.
- Engage in the research process and influence it to accommodate for more available and licensed data, software, and code.

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The training was organized into 3 units. Unit 1 covered the rationale and benefits of applying open licenses to research products. It also discussed common concerns of researchers on the one hand, and ways to alleviate these concerns and advocate for open licensing on the other. Unit 2 presented a license selection checklist and discussed each of the ten main factors to consider, from identifying the rights holder and the funder, publisher, and repository requirements, to data privacy laws, commercialization potential, and dual use issues. Unit 3 presented an overview of available open licenses, including the Creative Commons licenses, together with recommended licenses for specific research products and tools that help in the license selection process. The importance of metadata and machine-readable licenses was also discussed.

In their evaluations, participants commented on the relevance of the topic in general, on the value of the license selection checklist and the practical guidelines to select the appropriate open license, as well as on the usefulness of the examples of arguments to advocate for open licenses and how such licenses are beneficial to both the creators of the research outputs and the scientific community and the society more broadly.

Below, two examples of what the participants found most valuable about the course:

“The clear description of what licenses are available for what outputs, as well as the practical tools that can be used to help with the license selection process.”

“Explanation of licenses and counterpoints for convincing those who are reluctant to deploy them.”

Some participants also commented that, even if the content was already familiar, the training would help them teach or explain this content to others:

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“For me, being an RDM consultant/trainer and test user, is was not so much the content that was important or new but how it was presented. I am taking some good ideas with me, thank you!”

Finally, participants also remarked that the training was introductory, so most suitable to people new to the topic of licensing, and that a longer training would allow a more in-depth examination of the issues involved, including more real-life examples and more group activities and discussions.

3 Alignment with the MVS data steward

In this section we explore further the alignment between the activities described in the MVS for Data Steward, as a coordinator and embedded, and the training materials used on the pilot. Particular attention is paid to which activities are covered and which, if any, content is missing in the MVS.

3.1 Which skills and competencies from the training materials are missing in the MVS based on feedback from participants?

The topic of open licenses for data, software, and code (and copyright and intellectual property rights more generally) is considered by the participants as important and useful to data stewards and others working with research data and research software. This is worth noting because currently the Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) for Data Stewards licensing is only explicitly acknowledged in the Embedded Data Steward profile under main activities in regards to data management planning. Understanding how to select, apply, and advocate for open licenses for various types of research outputs is an essential skill of data stewards. This is especially true in the context of Open Science, in which open licenses both enable and encourage reuse of research outputs. This critical role of licensing is acknowledged in the FAIR principle R1.1 for both research data (*“R1.1. (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license”*) and research software (*“R1.1. Software is given a clear and accessible license”*).

One of the pilot’s participants confirmed the relevance of open licensing to Data Stewards in their evaluation:

“As a Data Steward, I must remain well-informed about the areas you've mentioned. However, my primary focus on addressing the needs of researchers often limits my capacity to update my knowledge base. Consequently, your course is critical in helping me refresh and expand my

understanding. The tips and insights you provide are invaluable, enabling me to enhance my interactions and discussions with the researchers I support.”

Subsequently, a suggestion would be to include additional text regarding licensing as a part of the essential skills for data stewards. It is recognised that the MVS is the minimum skills needed, so the additional text should reflect that. An example of this could be: Working knowledge of copyright and licensing as it relates Open Science and other research products.

3.2 Comparison of the MVS Data Steward and Learning Path for DS

The pilot learning path provides more intermediary material that goes beyond the MVS. Table 4, below, lists how the learning path is supporting elements of the MVS.

Table 4: How the learning path supports the MVS Data Steward

<p>This learning path contributes to the following open science outcome for a Data Steward:</p> <p>Research data and related digital objects are effectively managed to ensure their suitability for curating, sharing, and reuse, and potential impacts towards advancement of research methods appropriate to the discipline(s). Digital research objects are made as FAIR and open as possible, and as closed as necessary</p>
<p>The learning path provides material that would help the Coordinator and Embedded Data steward in the following main activities:</p> <p><i>Coordinator Data Steward:</i></p> <p>Develops institutional guidance on Data management Planning, e.g. templates offering cross-domain knowledge to contextualise data handling and advice on planning how to use local services or infrastructure.</p> <p>Understands research stakeholder needs and contributes to developing, implementing and monitoring Data Policy and Governance, along with</p>

service level management to support this.

Embedded Data Steward:

Develops Data Management Plans templates tailored for research teams, offering support in writing a DMP according to the relevant template. Includes **provision for archiving and FAIR sharing** (standards, metadata exposure, PIDs, **licensing**, data repository management/selection)

Implements **good practice on data and/or software/code** during proposal development for funders, and as a regular aspect of doing research, and liaises with other experts inside and outside the institute to adopt effective solutions to challenges.

Identifies gaps and takes action to ensure **ethical conduct and awareness of the potential impacts of data reuse**, management and sharing on wider society.

Supports researchers on **legal and regulatory compliance** aligning local practices with these through connections with the institutional privacy officers, legal advisers, and research ethics bodies.

Essential skills and competencies covered are:

Service provision to support specific Open Science practices including: applying **FAIR** and CARE principles, **Open Access (publishing)** , **data curation and preservation**

Knowledge brokering about Research Data Management, (personal) data governance and ethics, including to understand information security challenges, and provide access risk assessment and mitigation

Mentoring on open and fair methods, to develop professional practice including knowledge/awareness of programming, FAIR code and FAIR software and use of standards and ontologies.

Advocacy, analysis and assessment on FAIR data criteria, FAIR code and software preservation.

Stakeholder engagement and collaboration building strategic relationships, bridging needs, and speaking and presenting to data creators, users, and research stakeholders about the value of good data management.

Creativity, critical and analytical thinking, curiosity, openness, and cultural competence with a willingness to learn.

As indicated above, the proposed learning path offers the possibility of acquiring intermediate skills, beyond those proposed in the MVS. Below, Table 5, is a list of skills from MVS's Essential skills and competences that are aligned with the skills acquired as a result of the learning path.

Table 5. The alignment between the MVS skills and competencies and the training materials

MVS's Essential skills and competencies	Covered in training material skills
Service provision to support cross-domain/domain specific Open Science practices including: use of FAIR and CARE principles, Open Access, data optimization, data preservation, archiving and responsible re-use	Data & software policy; Knowledge to contextualise FAIR principles to legal domain (licensing)
Knowledge brokering about Research Data Management (personal) data governance and ethics, Open Science data publication and exchange(sharing) services, intellectual property rights, information security and risk management.	Knowledge to contextualise FAIR principles to legal domain; Information security
Awareness raising among data creators and users, researchers, organisational colleagues, and decision-makers of the value of good data management.	Knowledge of preservation for FAIR research outputs (selection of appropriate licenses)
Knowledge/awareness of	Software preservation; Metadata

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<p>programming, FAIR code and FAIR software and use of standards and ontologies</p>	<p>exposure (knowledge of machine-readable licenses)</p>
<p>Advocacy, analysis and assessment on FAIR data criteria, FAIR code and software preservation.</p>	<p>Awareness about advocacy for licensing</p>

4 Lessons learned and recommendations

In this section, we summarise our lessons learned from the pilot with the aim to optimise the efficiency of the hosting a ToT event. Further, we recommend adaptations to the training materials and ultimately additions to the MVS Steward.

4.1 Operational efficiency

The BBB adds a layer of complexity to teaching online. The instructor and facilitator need to invest time in using the BBB and guiding participants in how to link to and from the learning management system, where learning materials are published. When teaching online, it is important to create a comfortable learning environment, where the learners can focus on the materials. The technical platform must not distract from the learning experience or the quality of the training for learners and the pedagogical strategies of the instructor.

Even though we technical challenges, the pilot has contributed to our better understanding of the use and limitations of the BBB. We are confident in, that through our collaboration with GARR on this ToT processes around the use of BBB will be tested further and technical glitches reduced in the long run. We therefore recommend that everyone in Skills4EOSC needs:

- sufficient training on the BBB
- sufficient practice on the BBB - for example: the WP meetings could be on the BBB, to let all of us get familiar with it and practice using the various features
- Sufficient practice using the Learning Platform
- Awareness that creating learning activities and adding content to the Learning Platform takes time that needs to be allocated in the development of the learning path

4.2 Adaption of Learning Path

Further adaptations of the training materials are recommended to reduce the amount of content and use more time on discussions. Most of the content addressed licensing data, develop more indepth material about software and code.

As learners come to the training with different levels of knowledge of the topics, use effort facilitating the discussion groups to ensure assignments are understood and conversations are flowing.

4.3 Revision of the MVS Data Steward

The ToT pilot addressed only a small sub-set of skills described in the MVS Data Steward. The MVS DS deals with skills and competencies in a fairly general way. The training material on the other hand is more operational, showing use cases where the arguments for convincing people to use the licenses are clearly identified (slides 16 and 20). We recommend including additional text in the MVS regarding licensing as a part of the essential skills for data stewards, for example “Working knowledge of copyright and licensing as it relates Open Science and other research products”. Hence, the MVS would gain in precision by proposing a section dedicated to the legal aspects of the RDM, in particular concerning the dissemination and sharing of FAIR data in compliance with legal recommendations (obligations).

If anything, the training exemplifies how much knowledge is needed for each single concept listed in the MVS as this learning path provides more intermediary material that goes beyond the MVS and is also relevant for MVS for Legal Experts.

We consider the training materials also to be in alignment with the MVS for Legal Experts as a supplement to their technical skills and competencies in copyright licensing rules and existing frameworks. Likewise the materials,

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especially unit 1 concerning why researchers should license their research outputs and common myths why not to do so, are highly relevant for ELSI professionals to further their understanding of the psychosocial-disciplinary context and concerns of the researcher.

5 Sources for Learning Path Development

The learning path described in this report builds on the following sources of information:

The Moodle created for the pilot, published on the Skills4EOSC Learning Platform: <https://learning.skills4eosc.eu/course/view.php?id=29>

The Moodle contains slides and learning activities used during the pilot. The training materials used in the pilot were adapted from the library of suggested materials created in the T4.2, below.

Library of suggested materials created by T4.2

An editable version of the library of training materials including instructor notes published on Github and available via the following link: <https://task-4-2.github.io/Open-Licenses-data-code-and-software/latest/>

And also in Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/12703494>

These materials are intended to be used as a “pick and mix” slide deck that covers Open Licences for Data, Software and Code in a greater depth that is possible to communicate within a 2 hour learning path. The intention is, that trainers select content and adapt to their local environment.

Milestone: Technical skills are the bridge to reproducible research. An introduction for data librarians

Lead Partner:	DTU.DKB, T4.2
Version:	1.0
Status:	Version open for feedback (co-creation) within WP4
Dissemination Level:	Workpackage level
Document Link:	https://workplace.skills4eosc.eu/Products/Files/DocEditor.aspx?fileid=8102

Deliverable Abstract

This short report invites comment on the Learning Path for Data Librarians designed by the Skills4EOSC project, WP4, T4.2. the EOSC.

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DELIVERY SLIP

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosC-portal.eu/glossary>

<i>Terminology/Acronym</i>	<i>Definition</i>

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1 Executive summary

Overview of the Learning Path

On the 17th and 31st of January, an online learning path “Technical skills are the bridge to reproducible research. An introduction for data librarians” was conducted using Big Blue Button as the meeting platform. Participants accessed materials published on the Skills4EOSC learning platform. The training was facilitated on the 17th of January by Agnes Jasinska (DCC), Tuulikki Alamettälä (TUNI) and on the 31st of January by Vojdán Kjørveziroski (UKIM) and Mareike Buss (CBS). Technical support was provided by Andrea Corleto (GARR).

The content was divided into three units, taught over two days. The units delve into the theoretical and practical aspects of supporting reproducibility in data management workflows. It covers the concepts of reproducibility and replicability and the infrastructures needed to support reproducibility practices. Further, the course gives hands-on instruction in data hygiene and file versioning in the context of data management at an introductory level. Post-training, learners completed two homework assignments with Github and Jupyter Lab Notebooks, in which they modified the contents of existing file histories and modify them according to set out requirements.

Below are the main takeaways from the training as a whole. In the report, the evaluation of each unit is explored in more detail.

Participant Evaluation Results

- Participants appreciated that the comprehensive overview of the reproducibility crisis was complimented with an introduction to the technical skills required to mitigate them.
- The opportunity to discuss with fellow participants from various scientific disciplines was highly valued, as it showcased how methods and challenges across disciplines vary.
- The resource materials in the Learning Platform and in Github allowed participants to delve deeper into the topics discussed.

Main areas for Improvement

- Provide Real-Life Examples real-life examples, especially for complex topics such as Fabrication, Falsification, Plagiarism and the workflow in GitHub, to make the content more relatable and easier to understand.
- Integrate the principles and practices of Open Science throughout the discussions to emphasize its relevance to reproducibility and replicability.
- Include more detailed discussions and examples related to the challenges of reproducing qualitative research, using case studies or specific scenarios to highlight these challenges.

Alignment with MVS for Data Steward

In the MVS for Data Stewards the Data Librarian is described as an associated function title under the major category of Coordinator Data Steward and is in alignment with the skills, competencies and Open Science outcomes described in the MVS Coordinator profile. Based on the learning path we recommend:

- the addition of a basic knowledge of “closed” science research practices
- the addition of the skill that someone in this role be an “Open Science warrior.” While this may not be a common element to every data steward, we recommend it be included for those data stewards/librarians working specifically with research data.

Sources for Learning Path Development

The learning path was hosted on the [Skills4EOSC Learning Platform](#) and was adapted from content available in an [editable library of training materials on Github](#) developed by Task 4.2. Together, these sources provide a foundation for creating a comprehensive and effective learning path.

2 A brief description of the training (TtT) and descriptive feedback from the evaluation

2.1 Brief description of Learning Path

On the 17th and 31st of January, the learning path “Technical skills are the bridge to reproducible research. An introduction for data librarians” was held. The training was held online using the the Big Blue Button as the online meeting room and participants were asked to access materials published on the Skills4EOSC learning platform in preparation for the training. The training was facilitated learning, with the content divided into three units over two days, Unit 1 & Unit 2 on the 17th and Unit 3 on the 31st. Each unit contained slide presentations, discussions and learning activities. The three units addressed the following:

Unit 1:

Defining what reproducibility, and replicability are, explaining how they are different, and the potential benefits and barriers to reproducibility.

Unit 2:

Defining what reproducible research looks like in practice, discussing the reproducibility crisis and suggesting which remedies there are to overcome the barriers defined in Unit 1 at the level of data, code, research environment, institutional level and level of governance.

Unit 3:

The technicalities of reproducibility, particularly challenges related to RDM, file naming, file versioning in Github, data longevity and data hygiene with Jupyter Labbook in practice. After the training session, learners completed two small exercises. First using GitBlame and the second correcting an entry in Jupyter

Labbook supplemented with a short quiz in the teaching room on the Learning Platform.

Together, Unit 1 and Unit 2 constituted an introduction to the theoretical foundation of reproducibility, replicability and transparency. Unit 3 provided the practicalities of reproducibility, putting the theories discussed in Unit 1 and Unit 2 into practice.

The slides used in the training can be found on the Skills4EOSC learning platform and are published in the Skills4EOSC Zenodo library, please refer to Section 5 of this report for more information. After the training, the learners were invited to complete two small homework assignments. The first assignment is the use the Git blame functionality to detect whether any changes have been made to a demo repository after the content was initially committed. The activity its self focuses on the analysis of the history of two files. In the second assignment, the learner is invited to open an existing Jupyter Lab Notebook through an online service, execute its code and modify it according to the requirements of the assignment. There are no prerequisites for taking these activities. Both can be solved using a web browser and the learner has an unlimited number of attempts to solve the activity.

Agnes Jasinska (DCC) and Tuulikki Alamettälä (TUNI) were the instructors for Unit 1, Josefine Nordling from CSC taught Unit 2. Josefine is a Senior Open Science Officer from the IT Center for Science, Finland, and external to the Skills4EOSC project. Vojdan Kjorveziroski (UKIM) and Marieke Buss (CBS) were the teachers responsible for Unit 3.

Lorna Wildgaard (DKB) and Benjamin Derksen (DKB) were the facilitators and task leads. Andrea Corleto (GARR) provided technical support prior and during the training.

2.2 Participants evaluation of the training: Unit 1 & 2

Thirty-two learners participated in the training. Thirteen learners completed the evaluation, giving a response rate of 40%. Twelve of the respondents to the evaluation survey rated the training as very good or excellent, and 1 participant expressed the training was good.

Eight of the learners described themselves as having advanced to expert skills in reproducibility before the training and five described themselves as newbies or having basic skills, Table 1.

Table 1: Participants skill level before the training

	Responses
(0) None	0
(1) Newbie	2 (15.38 %)
(2) Basic	3 (23.08 %)
(3) Advanced	7 (53.85 %)
(4) Expert	1 (7.69 %)

After the training, we notice a slight difference in the participants rating of their skills, where one “newbie” has improved their rating to “Basic” and another participant has improved from basic to advanced.

Twelve of the participants achieved the learning objectives and found the training clear and easy to follow. These twelve participants considered the learning materials to be clear, the content relevant and easy to follow. One participant did not feel they achieved the learning objectives and strongly disagreed that the training materials were clear, relevant and easy to follow. Eleven participants agreed or strongly agreed the time allotted for the training was well chosen, two participants disagreed. Eleven participants agreed or

strongly agreed that the trainers were well prepared, one participant strongly disagreed with this statement.

2.2.1 Participants' qualitative evaluation of Unit 1 & Unit 2

In the evaluation, the participants were asked what they considered the most useful part of the training. They appreciated that the training provided a comprehensive overview of the reproducibility crisis, highlighting its importance and the challenges it presents. The discussions were particularly useful, as they refreshed the key issues at stake with reproducibility and replicability. The distinction between reproducibility and replicability was made very clear, underscoring that achieving reproducibility is never an easy task. It was beneficial that both units provided a mix of lectures and exercises, thus keeping the content engaging and informative. This blend of activities ensured a well-rounded understanding of the topic and highlighted the ongoing importance of addressing reproducibility in scientific research.

One of the standout aspects was the opportunity to discuss with fellow participants from various scientific disciplines. This interdisciplinary approach was enlightening, as it showcased how methods differ across fields and emphasized the importance of learning from each other.

Further, the resource materials allowed participants to delve deeper into the topics discussed.

While the training was overall beneficial, there were a few aspects that were less useful. Firstly, the introduction of many basic terms, although necessary and important, took time away from deeper discussions. Additionally, the section on Open Science (slides 18-19 in Unit 2) seemed somewhat redundant. Open Science is inherently a part of the reproducibility debate and should be integrated throughout the discussion rather than treated as a separate topic.

Below, is a summary of where the participants consider there is **room for improvement**:

- Use a Padlet to collect key discussion points
- More short activities like a poll or a Wordcloud instead of writing in the chat.

- Share the chat with the learners after the training
- More time and practice based on real-case scenarios to support skills progression
- Towards the end of Unit 2 add learning content about how librarians can help researchers answer the reproducibility challenges and potentials addressed through both units. This might require another unit.
- Consider reformulating slide 7, Unit1 (knowledge). It is harsh to state that no knowledge at all is generated from a single study when the team spent years to make their rigorous analysis even on only one data.
- More time for break-out, and the facilitators need to encourage participants join the rooms. It was experienced that during the training, some participants chose not to take part in the break-out rooms, leaving some rooms with only two active participants.
- Use Zoom, not the Learning Platform's teaching room (Big Blue Button)
- Include more qualitative research challenges and examples.

2.2.2 Peer review of Unit 1 and Unit 2

We invited five colleagues from the Skills4EOSC project to observe the training. These colleagues were not involved in the development of the learning materials. Their comments are summarised in the following sections.

Unit 1

What went well regarding the trainers slides, exercises and pedagogy

The slides were interesting and easy to understand, featuring original pictures that helped illustrate the concepts. Real-life examples were used to explain complex ideas, making them more relatable. The comparison between replicability and reproducibility was well-presented, aiding in clear understanding.

The approach of starting discussions in the chat before speaking was interesting. It broke the ice and allowed participants to think about their responses without

the pressure of speaking immediately. The instructors were engaged and enthusiastic, providing answers and feedback to questions, and acknowledged the contributions which encouraged active participation throughout the unit. The chat was also used effectively by the facilitators, who wrote the timeplan in the chat from the beginning, noted time allotted for breaks, thanked the participants for joining the training and providing contact information.

The theory was built up gradually with easy-to-understand slides, leading to an understanding of the concepts of replicability and reproducibility. Attention was paid to the chat, ensuring that all queries were addressed effectively. The transition between the two instructors was smooth, maintaining a steady flow of information.

The introduction to Activity 1 was handled well, reducing pressure on learners by emphasizing that there are no right or wrong answers and encouraging them to use their own words, no technical definitions needed which again encouraged participation. Activity 2 also resulted with many contributions in the chat, thus making effective use of peer learning.

The summary slide at the end of the unit was excellent, reiterating key takeaways and providing further reading and references. The first unit was covered well within the allotted time, in retrospect more time could have been given to the activities or reading comments in the chat aloud.

Overall, the sessions were well-paced, with clear explanations and a strong presence from the instructors. Acknowledging questions from the chat and thanking participants for their contributions helped create a supportive and engaging learning environment.

What could be improved:

- Address the challenges of reproducing qualitative research in more detail, as some comments from the participants highlighted this difficulty
- Give more time to let people finish their comments in the chat, when you can see someone is still typing.
- Include an introductory slide presenting all instructors and course overview to start the day
- Ensure the video is turned on for the presenter, because they seem more present.

How the training was received by the learners - positive elements

Despite participants not having the option to use the microphone, they actively commented and shared their views on the activities via chat. There was good engagement overall, with learners understanding the activities well due to the simple instructions provided.

Many participants were active in the chat, answering questions and contributing to discussions. However, less than half of the participants were actively engaged, which is understandable as some were there mainly to observe, and there will always be a few who do not participate. Beyond this, it is difficult to gauge how the session was received.

What could be improved

- Strategies/activities that encourage participants to turn on their microphone and webcam during in plenum discussion. In online training sessions, where people do not know each other, there is a reluctance to be “in the spotlight” so to speak.

Unit 2

What went well regarding the trainers slides, exercises and pedagogy

The instructor effectively picked up and responded to the written chats from the participants, ensuring that all comments were addressed. Overall, the presentation was very good, with clear and easy-to-understand explanations and

great take-aways. The instructor provided a detailed description of what would happen when entering the break-out room, including the technical information about using the Big Blue Button (the part about it opening in another browser window) which was helpful.

Additionally, the instructor thanked the learners for their participation, creating a positive and encouraging atmosphere. She also briefly mentioned a topic from Unit 1 that would be built upon, providing continuity and context for the learners.

What could be improved:

- Interesting but quite text heavy slides. Adding animations on the slide could help to ease the text, or, have had less text or simpler images or pull out the key information and presenting it bite sized.
- The slide on Fabrication, Falsification, Plagiarism could have benefited from real life examples of cases.
- The unit could have included an activity to give a break in the theory. Perhaps an activity to check in with participants and gauge their understanding.
- Even though the instructor explained the technicalities of the break-out rooms, some participants joined in 'listening' mode only. The same issue occurred in the main chat when one member could not speak up due to joining in listening mode only. One solution could be to send a short "how-to" guide out before the training.

How the training was received by the learners - positive elements

There were fewer engagement opportunities in this unit, except near the end. It is hard to comment on how learners received the training overall, but they seemed engaged via the chat, and the subgroup interactions were good. Near the end, learners commented that everything was clear and that they found the morning interesting.

However, less than half of the participants were active. In online training there will always be some who prefer to listen and not participate.

What can be improved

- Some participants chose not to take part in the break-out rooms, leaving some rooms with only two active participants. Facilitators and instructors need to visit the rooms or ask in advance, who will join the rooms and group these people together. The, people who are not prepared can be given another activity so they get the opportunity to engage with the learning materials.
- P- hacking exercise: encourage the learners to choose one person in their break-out group to report what they talked about or prepare them to write in the chat so they can copy/paste their thoughts quickly.
- The cell line case study was well explained during the training but perhaps was too complex. In the sub-group the participant commented it was hard to understand and hard to identify what was the problem. The other case study on p-value was much more easier to digest and interesting to read.
- It was a great way to end with giving the learners information about the next training and the content of the training

2.3 Participants evaluation of the training: Unit 3

Twenty-one learners returned for Unit 3. Fifteen learners completed the evaluation, giving a response rate of 71 %.

The learners rated their skills before and after the training as presented in Table 2, below. The results indicate that communicating the content through open discussion, practical examples, best practices, and hands-on exercises resulted in a clear positive shift in the confidence the learners have in their skills.

Table 2: Participants skill level prior to and after the training, n15

Skill level	Prior to training	After training
None	1 (6.67%)	0
Newbie	7 (46.67%)	1 (6.67%)
Basic	5 (33.33%)	7 (46.67%)
Advanced	2 (13.33 %)	7 (46.67%)
Expert	0	0

The participants rated the training as Good (1/15), Very Good (7/15), and Excellent (7/15). They all indicated that they achieved the learning objectives and the training was easy to follow. Thirteen of the fifteen learners who completed the evaluation considered the learning materials to be clear and the content relevant. Although 12 learners responded that the time allotted for the training was well chosen, three disagreed indicating in the qualitative analysis the need for more time and suggest a slower tempo. The learners strongly agreed that the trainer was very well prepared and likewise that the activities supplemented the trainer’s presentation of the technicalities of reproducibility.

2.3.1 Participants’ qualitative evaluation of Unit 3

The learners found several aspects of the training particularly valuable. They highlighted importance of both Git and Electronic Lab Notebooks (ELN) in the context of reproducibility. They found the training and activities at an appropriate level of difficulty, and praised the quality of the slides and the well-designed homework exercises. One learner noted that Unit 3 was particularly challenging for them, as it introduced new concepts in data science skills, yet they found it to be a great starting point for further exploration and will re-see the video recording of the training while completing the self-paced activities.

Unit 3 was mentioned as a crucial part of the learning path as a whole. The learners acknowledged however, that its effectiveness was built on the foundations laid in Units 1 and 2, and Unit 3 cannot stand alone.

In the evaluation, we invited the learners to comment on which aspects of the training they found to be least useful. Some felt that too much time was spent on explaining how to back up documents, noting that many countries have national storage services for researchers and other institutional backup tools. Organizing files and backup procedures were also mentioned as less useful by a few learners, but these learners also indicated that they were more advanced in their understanding of data management.

A couple of learners found the ELN part less beneficial, one of these mentioning that this last part of the training was a bit too advanced for them.

However, there were also students who couldn't pinpoint any specific part as being less useful, praising the coordination and progression of the sessions.

Below, is a summary of where the participants consider there is **room for improvement**:

- *Slide deck:*
 - Condense the information about back-up strategies to fewer slides
- *On the Git section:*
 - a clearer explanation for “good commit” practices, such as what makes a good commit, when to commit and how often.
 - Add a unit illustrating and describing clone/fork/push/pull/branch workflow
- *On the ELN section:*
 - Argue for how Jupyter Notebooks contribute to reproducibility, as they do not enforce a strict order of executions and are harder to version control with Git.
- *The quizzes and learning activities:*
 - The first quiz was not clear, consider reformulating to “Using the Git blame functionality, determine whether any changes have been made after the file was committed to the repository. Tip: analyse the history of line 32 in the file.”
 - More exercises – possibly a sandbox of exercises on the Learning Platform learners can try out at their own pace

2.3.2 Peer review of Unit 3

Three colleagues from Work Package 4, who had not had any part in designing the module, provided feedback on the delivery of the materials and the reception by the learners.

What went well regarding the trainer's slides, exercises and pedagogy

The trainer began with an introduction to how to unmute in the Big Blue Button and general housekeeping. This was followed by presenting the learning objectives and put the training in context of the previous units. Together, this introduction put learners at ease with the programme of the training and encouraged participation. Having the agenda in the chat from the beginning was appreciated, as was the clear division of the unit into sections with title slides and key takeaways.

The challenging topic of Git was explained thoroughly and clearly, using various modes of instruction, such as slides, animations, live demonstrations, and follow-up exercises. The slide on Git terminology was particularly well-received, providing a brief recap of previous terms before introducing new ones. The trainer's approach of showcasing practical examples without expecting learners to follow along immediately allowed participants to relax and focus on listening.

Data backup strategies were incrementally explained, with clear recommendations on what to do and what to avoid. Useful tools and strategies for using Jupyter notebooks were also presented. The explanations of topics and terms were clear, with many helpful examples provided. The timeframe and tempo of delivery was suitable and the use of the poll was engaging. The trainer managed to progress through the slides while keeping an eye on the chat, addressing questions without losing focus on the presentation.

What can be improved:

- Version control:
 - Add a semantic versioning number scheme to the slides (it was written live during the lecture, but it is not available in the slides on the learning platform).
 - Discuss the challenges of using semantic version control while writing office documents if the software does not enforce it during each save.

- File naming recommendations:
 - Add to not use emojis
 - The content jumped directly from file naming conventions to Git - maybe introduce other tools/ways to do this (e.g. Datalad)?
 - A key rule emphasized during the training was the importance of sticking to a naming convention once established, which could be added to the slides for reinforcement.
- Git features and terminology:
 - Establish what level the learners are on when it comes to Git, file naming and so on. Do they have experience with this already or is everything new? This information could be collected when registering for the course and used to inform the pace, level and examples.
 - Clarify for which types of files Git is a good solution. Git could be too hard to learn for some people. Thus if they primarily just edit .docx or similar, it is not the best tool
 - Add a visualization (e.g. for push/pull/local/remote). Explain the terminology with some (live) demo piece-by-piece instead of the full list of terms. Thus the slides defining the Git terminology will function as a summary.
 - Git branching in action: Demonstrate branching/merging with a small example (video/live demo/pictures) of 2 people modifying some code.
 - The content of the Git unit could be reduced, since this is only an introductory course.
 - An important limitation for Git was missing: Git is not well suited for large/binary files (unless Git-lfs or something similar is used). It is stated later while using Jupyter notebooks, but include this also into the Git chapter.
- Data backup:
 - Add a tip that the backup needs to be checked from time to time. There is nothing worse than having a backup and realizing, that the files you backup are not readable anymore.
- Pacing of the training
 - Presentation of the key takeaway in the end was rushed. Allow time for more details and give the learner time to read all the information on the slide.
 - Allow more time at the end for questions & comments

- Engagement of and communication to learners:
 - The bulk renaming examples were too small and couldn't be seen a small screen
 - The poll was fun, add more quick check-in activities like that. There was nothing during the first hour. The answers of the poll could also have been discussed in public, if there was time for it.

How the training was received by the learners - positive elements

The training session was well-received by the learners, who from the start asked questions which the trainer took his time to answer. The introduction began with Data Management Plans (DMP), which participants were already familiar with, and effectively transitioned from the theory from Units 1 & 2 to practice (Unit 3). Starting with the common task of naming files, supplemented with a terminology slide, made it easier for participants to follow along as the topics became more advanced throughout the training.

What can be improved

- Start each of the main topics with some survey or similar to activate the learners at the beginning, e.g. experiences with naming files. Alternatively use some quiz questions before continuing to the next topic to test if everything was understood.
- Allow more time for the training to include some smaller exercises for learners to use Git/ELN more quickly after something was explained. This would make the learners engage with the content and support deep learning.
- Reconsider the ELN example. The Jupyter notebook could also include loading and modifying data (e.g. removing outliers/faulty data). This would align well with the other key messages to not modify your raw data – instead modify them transparently while analyzing the data.

3 Alignment with the MVS for Coordinator Data Steward

In this section we explore further the alignment between the activities described in the MVS for Data Steward. In the MVS the Data Librarian is described as an associated function title under the major category of Coordinator Data Steward. Particular attention is paid to which activities are covered and which, if any, content is missing in the MVS.

3.2 Comparison of the MVS Data Steward and Learning Path of Data Librarians

The learning path provides more intermediary material that goes beyond the MVS. Table 3, below, lists how the learning path is supporting elements of the MVS.

Table 3: How the learning path supports the MVS for Coordinator Data Steward (Data Librarian)

<p>This learning path contributes to the following open science outcomes for a Data Librarian (as an associated title of the Data Steward profile):</p>
<p>Open Science skills and practices are facilitated and enhanced using, where appropriate, EOSC resources and services, including any relevant Open Educational Resources</p>
<p>Research data and other digital objects are effectively managed to ensure their suitability for archiving and sharing, and advancement of research methods appropriate to the discipline(s).</p>

The proposed learning path offers the possibility of acquiring intermediate skills, beyond those proposed in the MVS. Below, Table 4, is a list of skills from MVS's Essential skills and competences that are aligned with the skills acquired as a result of the learning path.

Table 4. The alignment between the MVS skills and competencies and the training materials

MVS’s Essential skills and competencies	Covered and built upon in training material skills
<p>Cross-domain/domain specific knowledge on Open Science practices, policies, and regulation and translating these to appropriate levels of the organisation</p>	<p>This training covers both the theoretical basis of reproducible and replicable research as well as practical means to check for issues in reproducible research workflows. By virtue of this knowledge, the Data Steward/Data Librarian’s ability to work with issues within and between research organisations to enable the Open Science practice of replicable research. Furthermore, the learning path lays out the landscape of science in its current form in the segments regarding research malpractice, pointing thereby towards the need for the reforms embodied in Open Science.</p>
<p>Service provision to support cross-domain/domain specific Open Science practices including: use of FAIR and CARE principles, Open Access, data optimization, data preservation, archiving and responsible re-use</p>	<p>The second half of the training covers issues in testing for issues with versioning, file naming conventions, that can have knock-on effects for the reproducibility of a given bit of research and its associated data.</p>
<p>Raising awareness of the value of good data management among data creators and users, researchers, organisational colleagues, and decision-makers.</p>	<p>Part of raising this awareness in the data steward’s career profile will have to come from knowledge exemplified in the two parts of this course. On the one hand, the data librarian/data steward will need good knowledge of the tangle of incentives and practices on the ground, so as to be able to be rhetorically effective. This is covered in the first part of this learning path.</p>

	<p>On the other hand, the data librarian/data steward will have to be able to come up with concrete and constructive interventions, such that this awareness can be realised in better practises. This is covered in the second part.</p>
<p>Training design and delivery to support Open Science practices, policies and practices</p>	<p>While this learning path can be used to train data stewards/data librarians on the importance of reproducibility in research, it can double as a template for teaching.</p>

4 Lessons learned and recommendations

In this section, we summarise our lessons learned from the training with the aim to optimise the efficiency and scope of the learning materials. The main recommendation is to acknowledge that learners come to the training with different levels of knowledge of the topics, therefore use effort facilitating the discussion groups to ensure assignments are understood by all participants and conversations are taking place.

4.2 Adaption of Learning Path

Course Structure and Content

- Integrate Open Science throughout. Instead of treating Open Science as a separate topic, weave its principles and practices throughout the discussions in both units to emphasize its relevance to reproducibility and replicability.
- Include more detailed discussions and examples related to the challenges of reproducing qualitative research. This could involve case studies or specific scenarios that highlight these challenges.
- Consider condensing the introduction of basic terms to allow more time for deeper discussions. Perhaps provide a pre-course reading list or glossary to familiarize participants with key terms before the training.
- Revise Slide 7 in Unit 1: Reformulate the statement regarding knowledge generation from a single study to acknowledge the effort and rigor involved in producing research, even if it does not lead to broad generalizations.
- Towards the end of Unit 2, include a section on how librarians can assist researchers with reproducibility challenges. This could result in a new unit.
- In unit 3 develop material on "Good Commit" Practices and include more visual or live demonstrations of Git workflows (push/pull/local/remote) and branching and merging. This will help demystify complex topics and make them more tangible.
- Make a clear argument for how Jupyter Notebooks contribute to reproducibility, especially as they present unique challenges like version control and execution order. Further, rethink the ELN activity so it aligns with key messages about data transparency.

Engagement and Interaction

- Use tools like Padlet, Menti, Canva, etc., for collecting key discussion points and use polls or word clouds for quick feedback instead of relying solely on chat.
- To encourage microphone and webcam use develop strategies to encourage participants to turn on their microphones and webcams during discussions.
- Facilitate breakout sessions by grouping participants who are willing to engage together. Consider assigning roles within groups (e.g., note-taker, presenter) to encourage participation in the main group.
- Provide a "How-To" Guide about the online learning room you intend to use for the training - a brief guide before the training that explains how to use the platform, including how to join breakout rooms, turn on audio, share screen and participate effectively.
- Extending time allotted for the training or reducing content would help to ensure that learners have time to absorb key concepts.
- Leave Time for Questions: Ensure that enough time is allocated for questions and interaction, particularly at the end of the session. This will enhance learner satisfaction and clarify any lingering uncertainties.

Activities and Exercises

- Dedicate more time to practice-based activities using real-case scenarios to help participants apply their learning.
- Include check-in activities to gauge understanding and maintain engagement throughout the training.
- Simplify or replace the cell lines case study in Unit 2.
- Incorporate more small exercises right after key explanations, such as practical Git tasks or ELN demonstrations.
- Provide a sandbox of exercises on the learning platform where learners can try out Git, ELN, and other tools at their own pace.

Feedback and Follow-Up

- As the activities were conducted via the chat, after the training, share the chat transcripts with participants to provide a reference for key points raised during the session.
- Use more polls or quizzes during the session to assess how the learners have understood the concepts and workflows. The purpose is to keep learners engaged and assess their understanding in real-time.
- Encourage Learners to Revisit Recordings: Given that some learners mentioned revisiting training materials, consider suggesting that learners re-watch specific training sessions or refer to the video recordings while completing self-paced follow-up exercises.

4.3 Revision of the MVS Data Librarian (Coordinator Data Steward)

The learning path touches upon a number of skills and knowledge described in the MVS for Data Stewards. The MVS for Data Stewards deals with skills and competencies in a fairly general way. Many of the references to Open Science In the first two units, the training material draws out the need for Open Science practices as a kind of intervention in current scientific research practice. After establishing the distinction between replication and reproduction in Unit 1, Unit 2 underlines why these elements are required in research in general, but especially in the current research context (see for example slides 9-15 in Unit 2). Unit 3 then dives down into concrete programmatic interventions to realise reproducible, replicable, and thereby open research outcomes. Based on the success of this narrative structure, namely the presentation of a problem and some practical means to solve it, we recommend:

- The addition of a basic knowledge of “closed” science research practices into the MVS such that the data librarian/coordinator data steward will be able to successfully navigate and mediate the arguments of researchers, who act according to a variety of incentives. These incentives are not always aligned

with Open Science, and the data librarian/coordinator data steward will have to be able to offer rhetorical rebuttals in training situations.

- In the draft Data Librarian MVS (unpublished work undertaken early in Skills4EOSC), we suggested a crucial skill was that someone in this role be an “Open Science warrior.” While this may not be a common element to every data steward, we recommend it be included for those data stewards working specifically with research data.

5 Sources for Learning Path Development

The learning path described in this report builds on the following sources of information:

The Moodle created for the training, published on the Skills4EOSC Learning Platform: <https://learning.skills4eosc.eu/course/view.php?id=47>

An editable version of the library of training materials including instructor notes published on Github and available via the following link:

<https://task-4-2.github.io/Technical-Skills-as-bridge-to-reproducible-research/latest/>

And also in Zenodo: 10.5281/zenodo.14893262

Skills 4 eosc

Milestone: Ethical, Legal and Societal Issues (ELSI) in Open Science: Asynchronous TtT

Lead Partner:	DTU.DKB, T4.2
Version:	1.0
Status:	Version open for feedback (co-creation) within WP4
Dissemination Level:	Workpackage level
Document Link:	https://workplace.skills4eosc.eu/Products/Files/DocEditor.aspx?fileid=8260

Deliverable Abstract

This short report invites comment on the TtT Asynchronous workshops designed by the Skills4EOSC project, WP4, T4.2.

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Milestone: Pilot learning path for Data Stewards

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DELIVERY SLIP

<i>Date</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Partner/Activity</i>	<i>Date</i>
<i>From:</i>	Lorna Wildgaard	DKB/T4.2	2025.02.05
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DOCUMENT LOG

<i>Issue</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Comment</i>	<i>Author</i>
<i>v.1</i>	2025.02.04	<i>Initial draft based on observations of the training by Benjamin Derksen Lorna Wildgaard and Mareike Buss</i>	<i>Lorna Wildgaard (DKB),</i>
...			
...			
<i>v.n</i>			

TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

<i>Terminology/Acronym</i>	<i>Definition</i>

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1 Executive summary

Overview of the TtT asynchronous workshop

On the 3rd of February and the 7th of March 2025, inperson asynchronous workshops were held at Copenhagen University Library (The Royal Library, Denmark) and Copenhagen Business School respectively. The participants were experts in Research Data Management, Law, Data Science, and research support officers specialising in ethical and legal protocols in research projects. All participants were employed at the two aforementioned organisations research support departments.

Participants accessed materials published on the Skills4EOOSC learning platform prior to the workshop. The materials were primarily produced by Sonja Filiposka (UKIM) under the advisement of two legal experts Kasper Drazewski and Marta Musidlowska, both KULEUVEN. The workshop was facilitated on both the 3rd of February and the 7th of March by Mareike Buss (CBS) and observed by Lorna Wildgaard (DKB) and Benjamin Derksen (DKB).

The asynchronous workshop followed the design principle “off the wall”. Off the wall workshops are design and thinking spaces in which participants exchange ideas and solutions, using predesigned materials which follow a sequential structure - no matter if on site or in virtual space. In an “off the wall” workshop, there is no instructor but a host (time keeper) that steers the participants through video lectures and activities plus facilitates methods of gathering up workshop discussions.

The workshops took 3 hours each, including feedback from the participants.

Main areas for Improvement

The workshops at Copenhagen University Library and Copenhagen Business School highlighted several areas for revision. The workshop can be opened up to a broader audience, including PIs, decision-makers, and legal experts, while reducing video time in favor of case-based learning and activities.

The workshop materials in their entirety would take a whole day to complete. Workshop materials. A facilitator is essential to guide the participants through the materials and act as a **content curator** to tailor discussions to fit the backgrounds of the participants. The materials can be used as “a pick-and-mix” to give a more flexible, audience-specific approach to workshop delivery. It could be beneficial to send a preparatory survey to the participants assessing their level of knowledge of OS concepts covered in the workshop materials thus helping the curator prioritise and select content.

The materials require better pacing, improved AI narration, and more inclusive coverage of qualitative research. Specific slides and modules need reordering, simplifying, more animations or graphics and guided questions.

Feedback from the participants

Participants in both workshops underlined the usefulness of potentially sharing a classroom with researchers as well as other stakeholders on the topic.

Participants in the second workshop at Copenhagen Business School had less of an understanding of Open Science concepts, pointing towards the need for a glossary of terms.

Participants from both workshops drew attention to the pacing and articulation of the AI narrator, stating that this mode of delivery made it harder to follow in some areas. They pointed to revisions in the slides as well as the need for extra guidance from the facilitator. They noted as well that it is artificial to draw a clean distinction between ethical aspects and legal aspects.

Comparison to the MVS Legal Expert

The workshop strengthens in particular, the ELSI professionals’ empathy and understanding of the challenges researchers face in working openly. During the workshops at Copenhagen University and at Copenhagen Business School the participants awareness about the different understandings and

application of legal terminology across the organisation, research projects, disciplinary perspectives was improved. The suggested MVS revisions include clarifying the distinction between skills and competences in GDPR and IPR, emphasizing their practical application for PIs. The term “empathy” should be added as a soft skill, as it enhances inclusive policies and researcher support.

The workshop’s relevance extends beyond Legal Experts to MVS RI professionals and Policy Makers, highlighting the extensive legal knowledge required for advising on research regulations.

Sources for asynchronous workshop development

The materials used in the workshop are hosted on the [Skills4EOSC Learning¹ Platform](#) and openly available in an [editable library of training materials](#) in the Skills4EOSC Zenodo. The materials include a Facilitator Guide which includes a list of materials, equipment and content the workshop host is advised to prepare before the workshop. Further, the videos used during the workshop are available on [YouTube²](#) and stored securely in Edumedia, a video library hosted by DKB, and can be embedded using this iframe:

```
<iframe
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¹ <https://learning.skills4eosc.eu/course/view.php?id=29>

² <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PL2mlGxrtBXixC-Vu96icYtAhlf-2y5xGA>

2 A brief description of the TtT asynchronous workshops and descriptive feedback from the evaluation

2.1 Brief description of TtT workshops

On the 3rd of February and 7th of March, TtT asynchronous workshops “ELSI perspectives in Open Science” were held. The workshops were in person and held at Copenhagen University Library, part of the Royal Library, Denmark and at Copenhagen Business School respectively. Participants were asked to access materials published on the Skills4EOSC learning platform in preparation for the workshops. The workshops followed the design principle “off the wall”. Off the wall workshops are design and thinking spaces in which participants exchange ideas and solutions, using pre-designed materials which follow a sequential structure - no matter if on site or in virtual space. In an “off the wall” workshop, there is no instructor but a host (time keeper) that steers the participants through video lectures and activities plus facilitates methods of gathering up workshop discussions. Mareike Buss was the host for both workshops. As the host is not required to be an expert in the subject matter addressed in the materials, all powerpoint presentations are prerecorded. The content was prepared by experts in the Skills4EOSC project and an AI-generated voice agent presents each slide.

The workshop is defined out of two main parts:

- Self-paced preparatory module (module 00) that contains links to video materials that participants need to review before coming to the asynchronous workshop. These materials provide introduction to the main concepts related to Open Science and ELSI in Open Science. These materials were made available to the participants in digital form at least one week before the workshop.
- The workshop materials include a videos playlist that is used during the workshop together with a supporting learning material in the form of handouts and learning activities. All handouts for the activities in the

various modules were provided physically to the participants during the workshop.

The asynchronous workshop itself consists of 10 modules. The aim of the modules is to provide the information on why ELSI is important in OS and how ELSI professionals can help support OS researchers. The modules are a mix of theoretical information and practical activities focusing on analysis of common ELSI related use cases and scenarios that OS researchers face in their everyday practice. These modules are:

01 – Open Science essentials: the participants are encouraged to join in an activity that acts as an ice-breaker and motivates them to start talking about what they know and have already learned about Open Science and how it is related to ELSI.

02 – The Challenges of Embracing Open Science: ELSI specialists working as research supporters may have a mix of perspectives on Open Science. The purpose of this module is to draw on the challenges they experience or predict in supporting Open Science in research projects and explore them in more depth.

03 – Challenges in applying Legal Frameworks to OS research: Navigating the intersection of legal frameworks and Open Science (OS) can be challenging for ELSI professionals. This module introduces the experiences of OS researchers through role play, helping ELSI professionals understand their motivations and challenges. By seeing OS from the perspective of the researcher, ELSI professionals are better equipped to develop appropriate practical approaches that support OS while upholding legal and ethical standards.

04 – Core values of OS research: The core values of OS are transparency, collaboration, and accessibility to improve the efficiency, reproducibility, and societal impact of research. There are ELSI considerations with each of these core values. In this module the participants discuss privacy, legal frameworks, and equitable access in the context of the OS research core values and how to achieved them while maintaining high ethical and legal standards.

05 – Open Science & ELSI What I need from you: Communication between researchers and ELSI professionals are key for the successful implementation of OS. In this module, the participants role play ELSI professional and researcher. They articulate the challenges they have met in OS research using clear concepts and defining terminology and explain what information they need from each other to solve the identified issues.

06 – Legal Issues related to OS Research: This module addresses legal issues in Open Science which occur when trying to ensure that research practices are ethical, transparent, and compliant with regulatory standards while promoting the responsible sharing and reuse of data. Topics include discussions of safeguarding participants' privacy through adherence to data protection laws, ensuring that intellectual property rights are respected through appropriate licensing and agreement, and how legal frameworks aim to facilitate equitable access to public sector data and support the responsible application of AI technologies.

07 – ELSI in OS: Use-case analysis: This module is designed to explore real-world use cases where topics discussed in module 06 have been successfully addressed, providing participants with practical strategies and tools. By engaging with these case studies and interactive activities, participants will gain a deeper understanding of how to uphold the integrity of research while contributing to the broader goals of open science.

08 – Ethics self-assessments in Open Science: This module focuses on the practical requirements for performing an Ethics self-assessment for EU-funded research projects. The aim is to gain an awareness of possible aspects to evaluate and possible issues in these projects. Participants are asked to evaluate two research scenarios from the perspective of assisting the Principal Investigator (PI) in preparing a self-assessment for a project based on a selection of questions from actual EU self-assessment forms. Engaging with these scenarios will allow participants to test their knowledge in real-world innovative research projects against an ethical background.

09-ELSI Tools and Best practices in Open Science: This training module focuses on implementing the Open Science principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”. It covers best practices, such as developing data management plans, using access controls, appropriate licensing. The FAQ activity engages participants in discussions around common dilemmas, such as sharing sensitive data and managing conflicting guidelines. The module aims to equip the participants with practical strategies on how to support researchers in balancing openness with necessary restrictions.

10 – Wrapping up: There is a complex interplay between Open Science principles and the ethical, legal, and societal implications they entail. Open Science practices, such as data sharing and transparency, should be balanced with privacy concerns, intellectual property rights, and regulatory compliance. We sum up this workshop by briefly emphasising the need for practical strategies and infrastructures for navigating these challenges, including developing data sharing agreements, addressing ethical dilemmas in research dissemination, and understanding the broader societal impact of open science initiatives.

The materials used in the workshops can be found on the Skills4EOSC learning platform and are published in the Skills4EOSC Zenodo library, please refer to the Executive Summary of this report for more information.

2.2 Workshop at Copenhagen University Library

Four out of nine invited ELSI professionals and Research Support staff took part in the workshop. The profile of the participants were: An ELSI professional from Copenhagen University specialising in support regarding ethical protocols, two data managers from the University Library, a chef research support consultant/engineer from the datalab at the Humanities, one inhouse lawyer specialising in GDPR plus the facilitator, who was a research support officer from Copenhagen Business School.

The workshop took three hours and was held on the 3rd of February, 09:00 am to 12:00 pm, in the teaching room at the University Library, which is a flexible space where the chairs, tables, screens and white boards can easily be moved around. Coffee, tea and snacks were provided.

2.2.1 Observations of the participants' interaction with the workshop materials

01 – Open Science essentials:

The softball, ice-breaker activity was effective despite the participants' diverse backgrounds. While some were legal experts in specific areas, others experts in one discipline while some had interdisciplinary knowledge.

During the ice breaker activity, the topic of FAIR was chosen. The discussion on FAIR principles highlighted varying levels of familiarity among participants. When one participant unfamiliar with FAIR threw the ball, the receiving participant provided a brief introduction and practical examples. This sparked a dialogue on data quality, quality assurance, and local challenges, including available tools.

In the next topic, OS principles, participants explored the inclusion of citizens in research. While acknowledging the value of public participation, they also discussed the potential biases, as only certain segments of the Danish population might be actively involved. The tension between information security and research openness emerged as a key issue, alongside the assumption that data transparency naturally leads to reuse.

Conversations about OS stakeholders questioned the broader purpose of research. Participants reflected on the tendency to focus intensively on their own work without considering its long-term use and impact. Recognizing research as part of a larger system was seen as crucial. Participants noted that research collaborations often introduce unforeseen challenges, making it necessary to continuously update documentation. In clinical research, adherence to good clinical practice is vital, yet researchers often struggle with proper protocol documentation, leading to potential database contamination with poor-quality datasets.

Discussions quickly became political however, touching on institutional guidelines and infrastructure in the light of the current administration reform at the university. The facilitator had to actively keep the discussion on track and encourage the participants to choose new topics. However, it became clear from the very start of the workshop that learning happened during the practical activities and not when watching the videos.

02 – The Challenges of Embracing Open Science:

In the module, the participants noted in a fish-shaped template the concerns they have about ELSI aspects in Open Science. This is called the “Stinky Fish” activity, which we returned to at the end of the workshop to find out if their concerns had become less or increased. During the “Stinky Fish” activity, participants noted topics such as data quality, the risk of scooping, the challenges of anonymizing personal data, and the reuse of datasets across disciplines. Questions were raised about how to share data responsibly, whether Open Science is possible without strict control over personal data,

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and the inherent competitiveness of research. A recurring theme was whether datasets, initially collected for specific purposes, could or should be repurposed, and how to ensure that participants consent to such reuse.

The Stinky Fish

That thing that you carry around but don't like to talk about;

but the longer you hide it, the stinkier it gets.

You should acknowledge and deal with it.

This Photo by Unknown Author is licensed under CC BY-NC-ND

The format of the activity prompted reflection on whether each fish should represent a single concern or if multiple ideas could be assigned per fish. Additionally, the facilitation of the session emerged as a key consideration.

While discussion was lively, a structured approach was needed to ensure all participants had a chance to contribute. Without moderation, conversations risked running over time, potentially leaving quieter participants without an opportunity to share their perspectives. Those who hesitated to speak until the end sometimes found their contributions cut short due to time constraints, emphasizing the importance of structured facilitation and timekeeping.

Despite these challenges, the activity successfully deepened previous discussions from the softball game. The participants eagerly suggested solutions to concerns from their own experiences.

03 – Challenges in applying Legal Frameworks to OS research

This module was a 16 minute long video powerpoint presentation including a 3 minute discussion. The speaker was an AI voice agent.

04-Core values of Open Science Research

This module was a 17 minute long video powerpoint presentation. The speaker was an AI voice agent.

A key takeaway from module 03 and module 04 was the importance of clear communication regarding slide duration – either by the host or in the actual slide presentation. Participants were unsure how long they needed to focus on each slide—whether for five minutes or for fifteen. During the video presentations, the participants looked at their computers, phones, etc.

The effectiveness of the slides themselves is another point of consideration. Across both modules, the speech pattern of the AI-agent detracted from some of the content. It is difficult to listen to the automated voice and digest the information over longer periods of time. Further the amount of information was overwhelming, and was often presented as a list, and sometimes the order of the points discussed on the slide did not always

logical, leading to participant fatigue. Additionally, the use of long, complex sentences—particularly those resembling bureaucratic "EU speak"—risked alienating participants who were already familiar with the subject matter.

On a positive note, the rhetorical style of the text was convincing. However, balancing the length of the video, the scope of the content and the language is essential to keeping engagement of the participants.

05 – ELSI & OS: What I need from you

The use of empathy in this module proved effective, as participants attempted to step into someone else’s shoes. However, the exercise was somewhat unbalanced, as one group spoke on behalf of their own experiences while others were asked to adopt the researcher’s perspective. Although the group discussions were though very lively, adjustments to the facilitation could help create a more even engagement, ensuring that all perspectives—both from researchers and other stakeholders—are equally explored.

Note – after the completion of the 5th module, there was 30 minutes left of the workshop. Consequently, we chose not to complete modules 06, 07 and 08 and went straight to module 9.

09_Module 9: ELSI tools and best practices in OS

In this module, there is an FAQ activity in which the participants are asked to identify possible ethical and legal dilemmas in a short description of an Open Science research project. However, we did not get as far as doing the activity, as the terminology used on the slides presenting the activity created a somewhat heated, but informative, discussion amongst the participants about the correctness of the information in the activity.

During the FAQ 1 exercise, it became clear that certain terms and concepts needed clarification. The slide conflated GDPR, consent, and anonymisation, which led to misunderstandings. Legally, GDPR governs data usage, not

participation in a project, and mixing these concepts resulted in an inaccurate presentation. To improve clarity, GDPR and anonymisation should be treated separately. Participants also discussed the distinctions between anonymisation, pseudonymisation, and relative anonymisation, as well as how researchers and ELSI (Ethical, Legal, and Social Implications) experts interpret these terms differently. This sparked a discussion, highlighting the need to refine the material for accuracy and clarity.

FAQ 2 addressed the complexities of handling and sharing sensitive data. The session raised questions about defining sensitive data, distinguishing between sharing within a research team versus making data publicly available, and determining whether fully anonymised data can still be safely shared. Participants considered the legal and ethical implications, including the risks of over-anonymisation rendering data unusable. The role of the data processor (datahandler) and responsibilities for secure sharing—such as encryption and controlled access—were discussed in detail. Additionally, the importance of understanding the underlying need for data sharing (e.g., from collaborators or funders) was emphasized.

Module 10: Wrap up

Finally, to close the workshop we revisited the Stinky fish the participants had drawn at the start of the day,

They all concluded that their fishes were still very “stinky” but agreed that they workshop had proven that knowledge of ELSI and support is dispersed across the university and there is a need to improve infrastructures, and decision-makers need to take workshops like this with research support to fully understand the investment needed in such infrastructures, citation:

“We are a lot of people with new knowledge, we need to keep in contact and try to put ELSI issues in OS on the agenda. We cannot lift these activities alone”

2.3 Workshop at Copenhagen Business School

CBS provides business-related education programmes and continuing education for the public and, in particular, the private sector. The five participants in the CBS workshop were from the legal department. One senior, three established and one junior member of the ELSI team took part in the learning path. They advise researchers on ethical and legal requirements in their research projects that can be in collaboration with industry. They work together with a separate research support team who have expertise in how to apply for funding (pre-award team).

Combining our experience and the feedback from the participants from the workshop at Copenhagen University, our approach to the training at Copenhagen Business School (CBS) was different. The Facilitator explored further the role of “Curator”, more details below and in Section 3 of this report. Being the Curator, she selected modules based on her knowledge of the profiles of the participants’, their areas of expertise and how they support researchers at their organisation. Accordingly, fewer modules were used in the training and only certain activities were conducted. As a result, more time was given to discussion which is where deeper learning happens as we observed in the first workshop.

The workshop took 3 hours.

From Facilitator to Curator

A facilitator is essential for the workshop, as participants would otherwise struggle to navigate the materials. However the role of the facilitator goes beyond guiding the participants through the content. The facilitator must understand participant needs and professional backgrounds, ensuring activities, terminology, and learning contexts are relevant, can be clearly explained and presented in the context of the participants. Accordingly, the facilitator takes the role of a “Curator” which demands they have professional knowledge of open science, stakeholder challenges and potentials and skills

as a teacher to be able to explain complex concepts and exemplify these concepts through examples the participants can relate to. Therefore their role is crucial in bridging differences in organisational perspectives, linking prior knowledge to new concepts and practices, fostering meaningful discussions, and adapting the learning experience to the group's specific requirements.

The approach

- The curator motivated the workshop, and advises on how to use the materials on their own after the workshop.
- The curator had an active role during the workshop, both guiding the participants through the activities and videos and also contributing with their professional experiences and cases about ELSI perspectives in Open Science in the context of CBS.
- There were no preparation materials, instead the participants were invited to view the materials on the Learning Platform after the workshop at their own pace
- Only selected content was used, described below. We chose to focus on the activities as these are not self-paced and require a group.

Module 00: Welcome

The Curator kicked off the workshop with short verbal presentation of what Open Science in the context of ELSI. The Skills4EOSC project was presented and the aim of the workshop was motivated. Accordingly, the video Module 00 was not used.

Module 01: Open Science Essentials

The participants enjoyed throwing the ball to each other and choosing themes to talk about from their own experiences. They engaged in constructive discussions. The AI voice/timer occasionally interrupted discussions, suggesting a need for smoother transitions. Despite minimal preparation, participants were familiar with key topics but acknowledged

gaps in their understanding, particularly regarding terminology and legal-ethical distinctions. For example, the FAIR principles needed to be introduced by the senior participant before the other participants could talk about the principles, revealing varying levels of understanding, and the need for further learning.

Discussions on legal issues in open science covered restrictions, licensing, and balancing GDPR compliance with open research, highlighting tensions between legal protection, data security, and privacy. Participants noted that acronyms and categories in the game were unclear and removed from their daily context, making them challenging to interpret. However, they recognized that researchers and legal experts perceive these terms differently.

In conclusion, the game fostered awareness of different stakeholder perspectives, including researchers, administration, society, and policymakers and what these perspectives could mean in the communication of ELSI requirements.

Module 02: Embracing open science

The curator began by showing the video and then conducted the Stinky Fish exercise in which she also created her own Stinky Fish.

The "Stinky Fish" proved abstract for participants without prior preparation or extensive OS knowledge. The participants agreed the ELSI professionals "do not have Stinky Fishes". The observation that "ELSI folks don't have stinky fishes as such" suggests that the exercise may be more effective if researchers are brought into the discussion to provide contrasting perspectives.

As a result the curator and the senior participant engaged in a case-based discussion, that turned into a panel debate where the remaining participants primarily observed. The activity revealed gaps in foundational understanding, such as the distinction between Open Access (OA) and Open Science (OS). The discussions covered research misuse, data security, and

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institutional workflows, with the CBS team noting that OS is not a daily concern for all in their career profile. The discussion further highlighted practical challenges, such as researchers using personal devices for CBS communication despite institutional restrictions.

The participants recognized the need for clearer, more context-driven materials, with stronger involvement from ELSI experts in development. The session ultimately evolved into an active learning experience, emphasizing the importance of establishing a shared foundational understanding before tackling complex OS issues. Moving forward, CBS participants aim to explore OS applications in their specific context and address institutional challenges and opportunities.

After Module 02 the participants needed a 10 minute break

Module 04: Core values in Open Science (shown before Module 03)

The 20-minute video was viewed in full, with discussions centered on the slide “Challenges and Considerations in Implementing Open Science,” which effectively wrapped up key points using pictograms.

The ELSI Considerations slides were particularly well-received for their visual clarity, aiding understanding. However, the AI voice was sometimes too dominant, giving too much information without sufficient alignment with slide content. For example, the graphics in the final 10 minutes effectively illustrated the complexities of Open Science but contained dense information that could be broken down further. Participants suggested splitting the video into two segments: the first 10 minutes before the "Stinky Fish" exercise and the last 10 minutes afterward. Care should also be taken to avoid unnecessary repetition.

Module 3: Challenges in applying legal frameworks to OS research

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The video showcases three researchers' experiences working openly and adhering to legal requirements. These video segments prompted discussions on clarity and relevance.

Segment 1 was well received for its clear explanation of Open Science pillars.

Segment 2 on child psychology was difficult to understand due to poor sound quality.

Segment 3 on FAIR use did not resonate with participants, who were unfamiliar with its requirements despite CBS researchers being mandated to follow FAIR principles. This highlighted a gap in understanding FAIR use and its role in their work.

Participants questioned the overall aim of the video in its entirety and whether they assumed ELSI workers were already engaged with Open Science or acting as advocates. The part about "Challenges in Implementing Open Science" was considered to contain too much verbal information without enough visual support. It was recommended to split this content into three separate slides (Legal Complexities, Ethical Considerations, and Funding Requirements), each with fewer points but stronger visual elements. Additionally, the AI voice was perceived as monotonous, leading to loss of focus. Finally, the distinction between legal, ethical, and funding requirements was seen as artificial, as all points ultimately fall under legal considerations.

To improve engagement, add more animations or graphics to the slides. Provide guided questions to help focus the attention of the participants during viewing and structure discussions afterward.

Lunch break (30 mins)

Module 07: ELSI in OS: Use-case analysis

The Curator introduced the FAQ exercise without a video, and divided the participants in groups of two. The Curator grouped up with the senior ELSI

participant. Each group worked on a specific FAQ, leading to a valuable exchange of knowledge, ideas and experiences between junior and senior participants, with insights contextualized to CBS practices.

- FAQ 1, the group presented their case and solutions, prompting a discussion among the curator and senior participant about stakeholder roles and the balance between archiving and research institutions.
- In FAQ 2, the curator enriched the discussion by drawing on real-life cases, deepening participants' understanding.
- FAQ 3 highlighted gaps in a mock-up form, leading to discussions on the templates CBS researchers use and distinctions between research ethics consent, GDPR consent, and journal code of conduct requirements.

The activity proved highly effective, with discussions planned to extend beyond the workshop, as participants intend to revisit the appropriateness of the templates they use in research support consultations.

Module 10: Wrapping up

The workshop was wrapped up by revisiting the Stinky Fishes produced in Module 02. Notably, not all participants actively contributed, only two added to their fish.

Preferring to discuss the workshop themes as a whole, the participants highlighted a fundamental gap in understanding researchers' everyday realities, emphasizing that professional backgrounds shape perspectives. Participants acknowledged that researchers would likely approach the workshop with different viewpoints and thus require a different selection of modules.

A key takeaway was the tension between Open Science and regulatory compliance, raising the question of whether adhering to OS principles might conflict with established rules and requirements—reinforcing that OS is a consideration rather than a working goal for the ELSI professional profile in Denmark. Additionally, participants reflected on the ELSI role as both necessary and potentially frustrating for researchers, often perceived as the

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raised finger of warning. However, they also recognized that compliance with rules ultimately supports good science.

3 How to improve the workshop materials

In the following section, feedback on the workshops at Copenhagen University Library and Copenhagen Business school are listed.

1. Workshop Design and Target Audience

- The workshop is also suited for PIs, decision-makers at the organisation, as well as Ethical and legal experts.
- The workshop takes longer than two hours.
- Include slides and discussions on how to ensure legal compliance in OS, among other things the necessary infrastructure (human and technological).
- There is potential to develop a version for lawyers unfamiliar with researchers' realities, helping them understand research workflows and priorities.
- Activities worked well, but videos took up too much time—preparatory readings would be more effective.
- Reduce the amount of preparatory materials by recommending selected materials for the participants.
- Add a Glossary of OS terms to the preparatory materials.
- The preparatory materials should cover GDPR, legal challenges in ethics, and consent distinctions (ethical vs. GDPR consent).
- Case-based learning would be beneficial, incorporating EU collaborations, international partnerships, and regulatory challenges.

2. Workshop Facilitation and Content Delivery

- The workshop is not a "plug-and-play" format; it requires preparation and tailoring to the audience by the facilitator.
- The facilitator role is in practice the role of a curator, which entails understanding the profiles of the participants before the workshop. The Curator selects content based on the participants and has enough knowledge of the subject to pose questions, and allow discussions to flow

when valuable. Consequently, know the workshop materials well enough to adjust the workshop agenda “on the fly”.

- If necessary, send a preparatory survey to the participants before the workshop to assess their knowledge and understanding of the concepts covered in the materials. Accordingly, use the responses in the selection of workshop materials and the delivery of these.
- Breaks should be integrated to maintain engagement.

3. Improvements to Workshop Materials

- Ensure the workshop title is consistent across all communication platforms – the Learning Platform, the welcome slides, email communication with participants and GitHub.
- Be more inclusive to the humanities and qualitative research across the slides and in the activities.
- Pre-workshop readings should be clearly structured. In the Learning platform the numbering refers to the origin of the content which comes from multiple sources. Participants found this confusing.
- At the start of the video presentations, inform the listener how long the presentation will take. The facilitator could do this or the information could be added to the first slide in the deck.
- Improve the intonation and pacing of the AI agent voice.
- **About the slides in Module 03:**
 - Shorten the video and reduce the amount of topics covered. Covering so many topics results in listing items to remember. Fewer topics will allow the workshop to delve down into more interesting aspects and improve engagement.
 - Break the content down over more slides with less narration per slide
 - Simplify the language and ensure each slide contributes new information.
 - Correct the order the information is presented on slide 8 “Strategies for Effective ELSI Support”. Either start with the first box on the slide or reorder the boxes in the order in which they are discussed.

- **About the slides in Module 04:**
 - As modul 03. Particularly the subtle changes to the content on the slides “ELSI Considerations” (slides 10 - 12) are not easily identifiable to the learner.
 - Split the video into two segments: the first 10 minutes can be shown before the "Stinky Fish" exercise and the last 10 minutes after the Stinky Fish activity.
 - Split the content “Challenges in Implementing Open Science” into three separate slides (Legal Complexities, Ethical Considerations, and Funding Requirements)
 - add more animations or graphics to the slides.
 - Provide guided questions to help focus the attention of the participants

- **About Module 09:**
 - The FAQs need better clarity, particularly on whether they refer to internal data sharing, external collaborations, or public dissemination.
 - The FAQs are too focused on health research—guidance on adapting cases for other disciplines would help facilitators make the content relevant. Allow the participants to read the handout *before* playing the slides which explain what they have to do. The handouts include clear concept definitions and present the context of the FAQs.

4. Lessons learned from the workshops that may inform the content of future workshops

- Researchers need clearer guidance on what they can and cannot do regarding personal data.
- The assumption that personal data can always be anonymised should be reconsidered, given rapid advances in technology.

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- Long-term data access and analysis are unpredictable—new strategies are needed to protect individuals while ensuring meaningful research contributions.
- Communication between ELSI experts and researchers is essential to clarify key terms like ethics, anonymisation, and sharing, as well as legal requirements under GDPR.
- The workshop should address regulatory complexities and how Open Science (OS) expectations vary by jurisdiction and discipline.
- Consider a code of conduct module, particularly for administrative staff.
- The workshop should also target research support professionals from different roles, requiring the facilitator is encouraged to tailor the content rather than a one-size-fits-all approach. Tailoring could include, adjusting the the content of the activities such as the subject matter of the cases or simply picking some modules out of the learning materials instead of using them all.

4 Alignment with the MVS Legal Expert

In this section we explore further the alignment between the activities described in the MVS Legal Expert. The term "Legal Expert" encompasses a variety of professionals, including Legal Consultants, Lawyers, Regulatory Affairs Managers, Data Protection Officers (DPOs), and Technology Transfer/IP Lawyers. Each role has varying degrees of legal authority, with some professionals, such as Regulatory Affairs Managers, not always licensed to provide legal advice yet having significant expertise in legal matters. A key aspect of this role is ensuring compliance with regulations such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), while also facilitating open access to research materials, data reuse, and collaboration. Legal experts also assist in aligning organizations with legal standards, mitigating risks related to privacy, intellectual property, and contractual obligations.

In the following comparison, particular attention is paid to which skills and activities are covered in the training and which, if any, are missing in the MVS.

4.1 Comparison of the MVS Legal Expert

Table 2, below, lists how the learning path is supporting elements of the MVS.

Table 2: How the asynchronous workshop supports the MVS Legal Expert

The workshop materials contribute to the following open science outcome for a MVS Legal Expert:

The organization will be equipped with policies, contracts and other instruments necessary to the realization of the legal rules and ethical principles concerning OS.

The asynchronous workshop provides material that would help the Legal Expert in the following main activities:

- Promote and support open access and **other OS-related legal and**

<p>ethical principles</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assess and address legal risks concerning Intellectual Property Rights (e.g., Personal and Non-Personal Data Protection and Governance, Licensing and Information Security • Develops policies, contracts and other instruments necessary to the realization of the legal rules and ethical principles concerning OS • Advises the organization on the compatibility of local practices with the current legal framework
<p>Essential skills and competencies covered are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good understanding of OS and its practices. • Ability to identify ethical issues and apply the necessary measures to address the existing and applicable ethical principles, frameworks and codes of conduct, including but not limited to the ones concerning research (eg the RRI Framework and the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity – ALLEA) • Ability to address legal issues related to personal data governance, including but not limited to the management of personal data, development and management of policies on privacy and data protection (eg consent forms, data policies, etc) and expert knowledge on the application of regulations on privacy and personal data protection <p>Soft/ transversal skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effective communication • Critical and Analytical thinking • Collaboration • Translating needs/bridging function

The workshop addresses the activities and skills above on an individual level, requiring the participant to reflect over their current practices and the regulations and services at their organisation. Below, Table 3, is a list of skills from MVS's Essential skills and competences that are aligned with the skills acquired as a result of the workshop. Primarily, through dialogue and roleplay the workshop, the workshop contributes to the development of the Legal Expert's soft/transversal skills.

Table 3. The alignment between the MVS skills and competencies and the training materials

MVS Legal Expert Essential skills and competences	Covered in training material skills
Good understanding of OS and its practices.	<p>Research Skills: The researchers perspective on working openly but still needing to adhere to the necessary regulations.</p> <p>Fundamental knowledge of Open and FAIR workflows and principles</p>
<p>Ability to identify ethical issues and apply the necessary measures to address the existing and applicable ethical principles, frameworks and codes of conduct, including but not limited to the ones concerning research (eg the RRI Framework and the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity - ALLEA)</p>	<p>Empathy and Understanding: Communication of and reflection over ethical issues in research projects and the complexities of opening research data and documentation in accordance with regulations and ethical principles.</p>
<p>Ability to address legal issues related to personal data governance, including but not limited to the management of personal data, development and management of policies on privacy and data protection (eg consent forms, data policies, etc) and expert knowledge on the application of</p>	<p>Translating needs and bridging function: Awareness about the different understandings and application of legal terminology across the organisation, research projects, disciplinary perspectives, research groups and individuals.</p>

<p>regulations on privacy and personal data protection</p>	
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4.2 Revision of the MVS Legal Expert

The workshop addressed only a small sub-set of skills described in the MVS Legal Expert, primarily through critical reflection and roleplay the soft skills of the Legal Expert were trained. Training empathy and collaboration in turn should feed into more inclusive policies and improved understanding of the challenges research projects face in application of legal regulations and working open.

We recommend including additional text in the MVS, making a clearer distinction between skills and competences in GDPR and IPR, as during the workshop how GDPR compliance and IPR is applied in practice in research projects is very important and a common issue for PIs, as they have different implications in different stages of the research life cycle.

Further, we recommend adding the term “empathy” as a Soft/transversal skill.

If anything, the training exemplifies how much knowledge is needed to be able to advise on application of legal frameworks and regulations. As such the workshop is also relevant for MVS RI professionals and MVS Policy Maker (in the decision maker and researcher role).

